

Healthcare serial killer or coincidence?

Statistical issues in investigation of suspected medical misconduct

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1. Overview

Justice systems are sometimes called upon to evaluate cases in which healthcare professionals are suspected of killing their patients illegally. These cases are difficult to evaluate because they involve at least two levels of uncertainty. Commonly in a murder case it is clear that a homicide has occurred, and investigators must resolve uncertainty about who is responsible. In the cases we examine here there is also uncertainty about whether homicide has occurred. Investigators need to consider whether the deaths that prompted the investigation could plausibly have occurred for reasons other than homicide, in addition to considering whether, if homicide was indeed the cause, the person under suspicion is responsible.

In this report, the RSS provides advice and guidance on the investigation and evaluation of such cases. This report was prompted by concerns about the statistical challenges such cases pose for the legal system. The cases often turn, in part, on statistical evidence that is difficult for lay people and even legal professionals to evaluate. Furthermore, the statistical evidence may be distorted by biases, hidden or apparent, in the investigative process that render it misleading. In providing advice on how to conduct investigations in such cases, this report particularly focuses on minimising the kinds of biases that could distort statistical evidence arising from the investigation. This report also provides guidance on how to recognise and take account of such biases when evaluating statistical evidence and more broadly on how to understand the strengths and limitations of such evidence and give it proper weight.

This report is designed specifically to help all professionals involved in investigating such cases and those who evaluate such cases in the legal system, including expert witnesses. It will also be of interest to scholars and legal professionals who are interested in the role of statistics in evidentiary proof, and more generally to anyone interested in improving criminal investigations. With such a wide range of audiences, it is inevitable that for some readers certain sections may seem more relevant, and some less so, but we believe it is important not to aim particular sections at particular kinds of reader. We want, for example, the barrister to see what advice we give to the expert statistical witness – and we hope understand it, at least in broad terms – and vice versa; we believe that is important in helping all parties to appreciate the contributions of others in reaching just outcomes.

Because suspicions about medical murder often arise due to a surprising or unexpected series of events, such as an unusual number of deaths among patients under the care of a particular professional, this report will begin (in **Section 2**) with a discussion of the statistical challenge of distinguishing event clusters that arise from criminal acts from those that arise coincidentally from other causes. This analysis will show that seemingly improbable patterns of events (eg apparent clusters, rising trends, etc.) can often arise without criminal behaviour and may therefore have less probative value than people assume for distinguishing criminality from coincidence.

Section 3 of this report will focus on the competing theories that are often advanced by the prosecution and defence when a medical professional faces criminal charges for killing patients. The prosecution's theory is typically that a medical professional, previously trusted to perform critical life-saving functions, has unexpectedly (and sometimes inexplicably), chosen to murder patients in his or her care. While history has shown that humans are capable of such behaviour, and there have indeed been cases in which, for example, physicians have murdered multiple patients, nevertheless proven instances are thankfully extraordinarily rare – a mere handful of documented cases, perhaps a dozen or so per year, among the many millions of healthcare professionals worldwide. So the prosecution's theory in such cases is often one that appears, *a priori*, to be improbable. Alternative theories – ie, that some unknown factors, or mere chance, caused deaths to occur in apparently extraordinary numbers among patients

under the care of a particular professional – often also appear improbable. So the assessment of the case invariably turns, at least in part, on a weighing or balancing of the probabilities of seemingly extraordinary events. Such assessments are challenging under the best of circumstances but become especially difficult when the evidence adduced to distinguish between the competing theories may be biased or presented in a misleading manner.

Section 4 of this report discusses the kinds of investigative biases that can arise in these cases. Our focus is on ways that investigators' desires and expectations may *unintentionally and even unconsciously* influence what they look for, how they characterise and classify what they find, what they deem to be relevant and irrelevant, and what they choose to disclose. Examiner bias is a well-known phenomenon in both scientific and forensic investigations. It arises in large part from what are known as observer effects, a tendency for human beings to look for data confirming their expectations (confirmation bias) and to interpret data in ways that are subtly (and often unconsciously) influenced by their expectations and desires. Statisticians have long studied the ways in which examiner bias can distort statistical evidence emerging from scientific and forensic investigations. In Section 4, we apply insights from this scientific literature to an analysis of the investigative process in the types of cases discussed in this report. We also draw examples from investigations of actual cases that illustrate what we believe to have been biased investigative processes and discuss how such biases can generate misleading statistical findings. It bears repeating that our focus in this section is on processes that can *unintentionally and unconsciously* influence the investigative process. We are not questioning the general honesty, integrity or good intentions of those involved in investigating such cases. We focus instead on investigative procedures that can distort statistical findings in ways that, while entirely unintentional, may nevertheless be important.

Section 5 of this report provides advice on how to improve investigative procedures in order to minimise investigative biases. While it is impossible to eliminate all human biases from a criminal investigation, there are a number of procedures that can reduce bias and thereby improve the quality and objectivity of the evidence emerging from the types of investigations we discuss here. We focus particularly on the advantages of blinding and masking procedures, which involve temporarily withholding potentially biasing facts from some of those involved in the investigation. We go on to discuss ways to reduce "tunnel vision" in which the investigation becomes a search for evidence confirming a particular investigative theory while ignoring or dismissing evidence inconsistent with that theory. We provide and explain advice on appropriate correct analyses of data, and discuss two worked examples.

Section 6 provides advice on evidence evaluation and fact-finding in these cases. We expect this report to be relevant and useful anywhere such cases may arise; hence we do not limit our discussion to the needs of a particular legal system, and expect our advice to be useful both in inquisitorial and adversarial legal processes. We believe the statistical issues in these cases pose challenges to legal fact-finders in every jurisdiction, whether they are professional judges or lay jurors, and are challenging for lawyers as well. Our advice focuses on identifying and appreciating ways in which statistical evidence may be misleading, and assuring (to the extent possible) that presentations of evidence are balanced in order to help triers-of-fact appreciate both the strengths and limitations of the evidence, and give it only the weight it deserves. We will provide examples of presentations and arguments that we consider to be misleading or inappropriate. We will discuss cautionary instructions that may be helpful to lay fact-finders. Ultimately, we hope our comments will help lawyers and judges, and statisticians and other experts, refine their presentation and evaluation of evidence in these difficult cases in order to better serve the interests of justice.

Finally, we draw together our main conclusions, and present a summary of our most important recommendations in Section 7.

2. “This could not have been a coincidence!”: The challenge of drawing conclusions from suspicious clusters of deaths (or other adverse outcomes)

In some cases suspicions against medical professionals arise for the very reason that an apparently unusual number of deaths occurs among their patients. In other cases suspicions arise for unrelated reasons and this prompts an examination of cases where a certain medical professional was on duty and this reveals an apparently unusual number of deaths. There is a statistical challenge of distinguishing event clusters that arise from criminal acts from those that arise coincidentally from other factors. Seemingly improbable clusters of events can often arise by chance without criminal behaviour and may therefore have less probative value than people assume for distinguishing criminality from coincidence.

Lucy and Aitken published an analysis of evidence used to prosecute medical professionals accused of harming their patients¹. They found (see p. 152) that “evidence of attendance” was “by far the most frequently occurring” yet was also “the most difficult type of evidence, both from a legal and epistemological point of view”. While other types of evidence may be presented, such as evidence of a criminal intent (*mens rea*) and the means to carry it out, or eyewitness accounts, these tend to be less than definitive for a variety of reasons, such as the difficulty of ascertaining retrospectively the exact cause of death and the uncertainty inherent in assessing human motives and behaviour. Statistics on the relative rate of deaths when a particular professional was “in attendance” may, by contrast, seem more objective and scientific, making statistical evidence the lynchpin of these cases.

Drawing causal conclusions from a statistically improbable cluster of events is often challenging, however.² A criminal investigation is analogous to a retrospective observational study. In such a study, it is possible to ascertain correlations between variables. The study might establish, for example, that the death rate was higher when a particular medical professional was present on a hospital ward. However, one of the fundamental principles of logical inference is that correlation does not prove causation. The increase in death rate cannot, in itself, prove that the professional in question was engaging in misconduct that caused the increase in deaths because other factors, known as confounding variables, might offer alternative explanations.³ Competent investigators are attentive to the possibility of confounding variables and may attempt to take them into account. Even if all known confounding variables are taken into account, however, there might be additional confounders, unknown, unmeasured, unmeasurable, or otherwise inadequately dealt with, that affect mortality rates when a given medical professional is on duty. For example, there may be changes in the circumstances and characteristics of the hospital for reasons that are not measured, or even not observable at all. So finding an association of a particular professional with high mortality rates cannot *per se* have a causal interpretation.

It is customary to compute the relative risk, which is the ratio of the death rate per unit of time when the suspected individual is on duty to the death rate per unit time when the suspect is not on duty. For example, an analysis in a prosecution against US nurse Jane Bolding (see box over page) found that

¹ Lucy and Aitken (2002).

² Wartenberg, 2001.

³ A confounder is a variable, not of prime concern in a study, that is associated with both the ‘exposure’ (eg presence of a particular nurse) and the ‘outcome’ (eg unexpected death of a patient). Neglect or inadequate attention to confounders typically leads to misleading conclusions about the causal effect of the exposure.

patients under her care were 47.5 times more likely to suffer cardiac arrest than were those of other nurses, and that “an epidemic” of cardiac arrests ceased when Bolding left the hospital unit where it occurred (Sacks et al., 1988).

To help the court interpret such statistics, experts often report a p -value, which is an estimate of the probability that the observed (or a greater) number of deaths would occur by chance, if the risk to the patients in question was in fact no higher than the risk to similar patients who were not under the care of the accused.

The case of Jane Bolding

Statistical evidence often plays a prominent role in the investigation of suspected healthcare serial killers. In 1988, Jane Bolding, an American nurse who worked in the intensive care unit of Prince George’s Medical Center in Maryland, was prosecuted for serial murder of patients, allegedly by administering lethal doses of potassium chloride. The key evidence against Bolding was the high incidence of cardiac arrest during periods when Bolding was on duty. Evidence suggested that she had been the primary nurse on duty when 57 heart attacks occurred, while the number during comparable periods when other nurses were on duty had never exceeded five. An analysis by epidemiologists from the U.S. Centers for Disease Control (CDC) concluded that Bolding’s patients were 47.5 times more likely to experience cardiac arrest than those of other nurses and that “an epidemic” of cardiac arrests ceased when Bolding left the hospital unit where it occurred (Sacks et al., 1988; CDC, 1985). Sacks testified at Bolding’s trial that “[t]he chances of [this large number of cardiac arrests] happening by chance is about one in 100 trillion.”

Other than the statistical evidence, the key evidence against Bolding was an alleged confession. During a 23-hour interrogation, Bolding reportedly confessed to killing two patients and agreed to write letters of apology to their families. She later retracted this confession, however, and it was excluded from the trial after a judge found that it had been obtained through illegally coercive methods that violated Bolding’s constitutional rights. Consequently, prosecutors had little to rely upon during the trial other than the statistical evidence. No one testified to seeing Bolding inject any patients with potassium chloride, and although post-mortem examinations showed that the patients had higher than normal potassium levels, it was impossible to determine whether potassium chloride poisoning was the cause of the deaths. Defence lawyers offered alternative theories for the elevated rate of deaths during periods when Bolding was present.

A judge, who decided the case without a jury, found the prosecution’s statistical evidence insufficient to warrant a conviction, saying “the state at most has placed [Bolding] at the scene of the offenses...but that is insufficient to sustain a conviction.” (Washington Post, June 21, 1988). According to the judge, the statistical evidence “failed to supply the missing link that would connect the defendant with the alleged criminal act,” and consequently “the state’s reach hopelessly exceeded its grasp” (AP News, June 20, 1988).

Sacks testified at Bolding’s trial that “[the] chances of [this large number of cardiac arrests] happening by chance is about one in 100 trillion”. Faced with such evidence, it is understandable that authorities may declare: “This could not have been a coincidence!” and conclude that the only reasonable explanation is criminal misconduct. Yet a judge acquitted Bolding of charges that she killed three gravely ill patients

and attempted to murder two others by injecting them with massive doses of potassium chloride, finding this statistical evidence insufficient to sustain a conviction.

As we will explain, there are a number of potential problems with computations and interpretations based on such evidence. Relative risk is difficult to compute in a manner that takes appropriate account of all relevant variables, and efforts to evaluate relative risk may be distorted by a variety of biases and predictable errors that can make such statistics misleading.⁴

Recommendations for appropriate statistical analysis are discussed in Section 5.⁵ We will leave those problems aside for the moment, however, in order to discuss a more fundamental issue: what conclusions can reasonably be drawn from a seemingly unlikely cluster of occurrences?

a. Seemingly unlikely coincidences can and do occur

It is important to acknowledge that seemingly unlikely coincidences occur regularly – in other words rare events do happen. The individual chances of winning a lottery, for example, are often extremely low, yet winners are declared regularly and it is rare that anyone takes the low probability of winning as indicating that the victory “could not have been a coincidence.” A California couple once managed to win two separate lotteries in a single day. According to one estimate, the probability of winning both lotteries by chance was approximately one in 26 trillion.⁶ Yet there was no general belief that this probability was low enough to rule out the possibility it was merely coincidence; no serious claim that it proved the lotteries had been “fixed”. It is therefore worth considering why the low p -value assigned to a relative risk analysis can be taken as powerful evidence that a medical professional engaged in criminal misconduct, while a similarly low probability of winning a lottery is not viewed as convincing evidence that the lottery was corrupt.

The difference may arise, in part, from our understanding that many people play the lottery. There may only be one chance in many millions of winning, but if many millions of people play, it becomes quite plausible that someone will, by chance, be a winner (and this holds even without the lottery operator engineering wins by eg carrying over unclaimed prizes to later draws). When suspicions arise against a medical professional, by contrast, our focus is on that single individual. We are not thinking about the likelihood that an unusual number of deaths will be observed somewhere among the patients of one of the millions of medical professionals in the world; we are thinking about the likelihood of so many deaths among patients of a particular individual. While we expect someone to win a lottery; we do not expect

⁴ This is a separate issue from that of how to report changes in risk. It is important to distinguish between relative risk and absolute risk to avoid misinterpretation. The absolute risk is the number of events (good or bad) during a stated period in treated or control groups, divided by the number of people in that group. The relative risk is the ratio of the absolute risk in the treatment group, divided by that in the control group. It is very common, both in serious studies and in everyday life, for a large relative risk to be reported for what may be a very small, even negligible, increase in absolute risk. See Appendix 2, and Spiegelhalter (2017). See also the BMJ blog article [Making a pig's breakfast of research reporting](#) which includes the sentence "This implies that every single portion of bacon increases risk by 20%, when in fact the study found that only increased consumption over time increases absolute risk by 0.08%."

⁵ See also the Inns of Court College of Advocacy/Royal Statistical Society report on Statistics and Probability for Advocates (2017).

⁶ See ABC News, [California couple wins two lotteries in one day](#).

any particular player to win; and by similar logic we do not expect a rash of deaths among patients of a particular medical professional.

This difference may be more apparent than real, however, particularly if an apparently anomalous number of deaths is the very reason that suspicions arose against that individual, or was the reason that such suspicions led to a criminal prosecution. It is unlikely that a 1-in-10-million coincidence will incriminate any particular medical professional, but given the very large number of medical professionals in the world, it is likely, perhaps even inevitable, that such a coincidence will affect the patients of some medical professional at some medical facility somewhere in the world.⁷ Consequently, if we take the 1-in-10-million coincidence to be evidence of medical misconduct, it is inevitable that we will falsely incriminate innocent people. Thus, the existence of a cluster of deaths among patients of a medical professional should not, in itself, be taken as proof of criminality. We are not suggesting that such evidence is worthless; indeed, as we will explain, it may have substantial probative value, but its value needs to be assessed carefully in light of the other evidence in the case.

b. The importance of avoiding illogical inferences from p -values

Suppose that an unexpectedly large number of deaths occur among patients of a particular medical professional. Suppose further that an expert concludes that the probability of so many deaths occurring by chance is only 0.000001, or one in a million. What can we conclude about the chances that the medical professional engaged in misconduct?

As mentioned earlier, there are a number of potential problems surrounding the computation of statistics of this type, p -values, but let us leave such issues aside for the moment and assume that the expert's probability is well supported by available data. What can we conclude from it?

People often think that a p -value tells them the probability that a coincidence occurred. So, it may seem reasonable to assume that the p -value means there is only one chance in a million that so many deaths occurred by coincidence and correspondingly 999,999 chances in a million that the deaths arose from some other cause. If misconduct by the medical professional appears to be the only plausible alternative explanation, then people might be tempted to conclude that the probability of misconduct is overwhelming (999,999 chances in 1 million). Thus, the p -value of 1 in 1 million might inadvertently be taken as proof that there is only 1 chance in 1 million that the medical professional is innocent of misconduct.

Research has shown that people are often tempted to think in this manner and have difficulty seeing errors in this chain of logic. Yet, this line of thinking is indeed erroneous and illogical, and may cause people to misinterpret the value of statistical evidence in ways that are dangerous and unfair for medical professionals accused of misconduct.

⁷ For a different example making a similar point, it is a simple calculation that if 1000 events occur completely at random in a year, there is a more than 93% chance that one of the 365 calendar days includes 8 or more events, yet the chance of 8 or more on one particular day is less than 1%.

The problem arises from misinterpretation of the p -value. The p -value is not the probability that a coincidence occurred. Rather, the p -value is the probability of the observed or more extreme evidence *if* it arose due to coincidence. In a case involving unexpected deaths, the expert might ask, for example, “what is the probability, by chance, of observing a given number of deaths (or more) among patients of a particular professional, *if* we assume that the rate of deaths is no higher than for patients of other similar professionals?” That is a different question than asking “what is the probability that the explanation for these deaths is mere coincidence?” Importantly, the answer to the former question does not tell us the answer to the latter, although people may have difficulty seeing why not.

Misunderstanding of p -values

Question expert attempts to answer:

“What is the probability of observing this many deaths (or more) by chance or coincidence IF the risk of deaths to the patients in question was in fact no higher than the risk to similar patients who were not under the care of the accused?”

Question people may mistakenly think expert is answering:

“What is the probability that the high number of deaths observed among the patients in question is explained by chance or coincidence?”

A p -value is a statement about a conditional (cumulative) probability – that is, a statement about the probability of one event (observing the data, or something more extreme) in light of another event (there is no effect of interest, only chance).⁸ People are generally familiar with the idea that the occurrence of one event may change our uncertainty about another event. For example, the probability of rain if the sky is cloudy will differ from the probability of rain if the sky is clear. But psychological research has shown that people often fall victim to a logical fallacy known as “transposing the conditional”, misinterpreting the probability of the evidence given a hypothesis with the probability of the hypothesis given the evidence. In a legal context, this error has been known as the “prosecutor’s fallacy,” the “source probability error,” or the “fallacy of the transposed conditional”.⁹ It is a widespread mode of reasoning, affecting many of the general public, the media, lawyers, jurors and judges alike.¹⁰ When incorrectly stating that the p -

⁸ The “another event” is a hypothesis; in some philosophical traditions, this would not be considered an event, but the logic that follows holds regardless.

⁹ Thompson & Schumann, 1987; Koehler, 1993; Balding & Donnelly, 1994; Evett, 1995.

¹⁰ For example, in the trial of Sally Clark for double infanticide, an expert medical witness testified that the probability that both her babies would have died from natural causes was one in 73 million (This figure has itself been widely and properly criticised, but that is not the issue here). If, as appears very natural, we refer to this figure as “the probability that the babies died by innocent means”, it is all too easy to misinterpret this as the probability (on the basis of the evidence of the deaths) that Sally is innocent – such a tiny figure seeming to provide incontrovertible proof of her guilt. For other evidence of the widespread appearance of this fallacy, and the difficulty people have in appreciating it, see Thompson & Newman, 2015; de Keijser & Elffers, 2012.

value tells us the probability a medical professional is innocent of misconduct, the error of logic is not so easy to see.

The error is to confuse or equate the conditional probability of event A, given that event B occurs, with the conditional probability of event B, given that event A occurs; the fault in this logic is easy to illustrate by inserting various propositions for A and B. Consider, for example, that the probability an animal has four legs if it is a dog is not the same as the probability an animal is a dog if it has four legs. The probability a person speaks Spanish if they grew up in Peru is not the same as the probability they grew up in Peru if they speak Spanish. With simple examples like these, the logical error of equating the two conditional probabilities is easy to see. But this same error underlies the assumption that the p -value tells us the probability a medical professional is innocent of misconduct, and in that context the error of logic is not so easy to see. A statistician testifies that the conditional probability of observing so many deaths (or more) is only 0.000001, or 1 chance in a million, if the deaths are occurring randomly at rates no higher than among similar patients of other medical professionals. Here it is tempting to transpose the conditional probabilities – to assume that there is also only 1 chance in 1 million that the deaths are occurring randomly given that so many deaths occurred.

Of course investigators and triers-of-fact in these cases need to evaluate whether the deaths in question could have occurred by chance. While the p -value does not answer that question directly, it may nevertheless be helpful by casting light on the importance of the death rate when considered in combination with other evidence in the case.

A final important caveat about use of p -values is that the assumptions underlying their calculation include that the test in question is the *only* test to be conducted. If large numbers of hypotheses are tested, then some will yield statistically significant results just by chance – that chance is precisely what the numerical p -value measures – so if several tests are conducted some adjustment for multiple testing should be used.

The correct way to “invert the conditional” and avoid the Prosecutor’s Fallacy involves a simple logic that is codified in what is known as “Bayes’ rule”, that combines the probabilities of the evidence given various possible explanations for the data (“hypotheses”) with the prior probabilities of these hypotheses, to deliver the probabilities of each hypothesis *given* the evidence. It is the same logic as is used to report a diagnosis following a medical test. In Appendix 4, Bayes’ rule is explained, using an example presented in non-technical language.

As we will discuss in the following sections, the connection between a p -value and the probability of misconduct by a medical professional becomes even weaker and more problematic when there are other possible explanations for the evidence (other than coincidence or misconduct by a particular individual), and when a p -value is calculated in a biased and misleading manner.

3. Competing theories

There are documented cases in which medical professionals have intentionally engaged in misconduct that put their patients at risk. A well-known example is that of Harold Fredrick Shipman, an English physician in general practice (see box below). In 2000, Shipman was found guilty of the murder of 15 patients under his care.¹¹

While it is important to acknowledge that cases like that of Shipman exist, it is also important to realise that they are extremely rare. Of the hundreds of millions of medical professionals in the world, the number who are known to have been serial killers of their patients is very small, a miniscule fraction of the total number. Consequently, in the absence of any other evidence of misconduct, the prior odds of any particular medical practitioner engaging in such conduct must be considered extremely low, of the order of one chance in millions.¹² As noted in the previous section, such low prior odds will often be difficult to overcome on the basis of statistical evidence alone. Even if there is a cluster of deaths among the practitioner's patients that is a million times more probable if the practitioner is a murderer than if the deaths occurred by chance, a logical assessment of the posterior odds might still conclude that the theory of coincidence is more probable.¹³

The case of Harold Shipman

There are documented cases in which medical professionals have intentionally engaged in misconduct that put their patients at risk. A well-known example is that of Harold Fredrick Shipman, an English physician in general practice. In 2000, Shipman was found guilty of the murder of 15 patients under his care. Investigators suspected he was responsible for the deaths of many others, perhaps as many as 250, making him one of the most prolific serial killers in modern history.

Concerns about Shipman were first raised by other medical practitioners, who noted what appeared to be an unusually high rate of deaths among Shipman's patients. An initial police investigation in 1998 found insufficient evidence to bring charges, but police subsequently learned that the wills of some of Shipman's former patients had been altered under suspicious circumstances to leave assets to Shipman, rather than family members of the deceased. Further investigation found evidence that Shipman had administered lethal doses of sedatives to healthy patients, and had then altered medical records to indicate falsely the patients had been in poor health. Based on this evidence Shipman was prosecuted and convicted.

In light of this grim episode, there were calls for improved monitoring of adverse medical outcomes, to allow dangerous medical misconduct to be detected earlier. For example, statistician David Spiegelhalter and colleagues suggested that statistical monitoring of patient death rates would have raised red flags about Shipman's misconduct years earlier, thereby saving lives (see Spiegelhalter, D. et al., 2003).

¹¹ See The Shipman Inquiry (2003).

¹² There is an extensive peer-reviewed literature quantifying this risk: see for example Forrest (1995).

¹³ Posterior odds are defined in Appendix 4.

An assessment of the posterior odds may change dramatically, however, should other evidence emerge that supports the theory of misconduct, such as evidence of the altered wills and altered medical records in Shipman's case. Evidence of this type, when considered in combination with the statistical evidence, may well make an overwhelming case in favour of conviction. Consequently, it is vital that suspicions raised by apparent statistical anomalies be followed by a careful investigation that looks for other evidence, such as evidence of motive, consciousness of guilt, or actual lethal medical interventions. Furthermore, as discussed in later sections, it is vital that such an investigation be conducted in a neutral, open-minded fashion to minimise bias. If such an investigation is conducted and no supporting evidence is found, that may be a strong indicator that the statistical anomaly indeed arose from coincidence, or that causal factors other than misconduct by the accused individual are responsible for what happened.¹⁴

Investigators should always bear in mind that there may be innocent explanations for apparent (and even striking) correlations between a particular professional's presence in a hospital on the one hand, and deaths, resuscitations, or other incidents on the other hand. Correlations might be caused by many factors, some of which might in principle be known, but still hard to take account of; some might be unknown altogether. Seriously ill patients on a medium care ward are quite likely to die at any moment, but the best medical professionals will not be able to predict exactly when. In one such hospital situation, statistical analysis of registered times of deaths shows that most deaths happen in the morning.¹⁵ The physiological explanation is that after some sleep, bodily functions resume, and organs close to breaking point can suddenly fail. In this hospital, there are many nurses on duty during the morning shift, starting at 7 a.m. and lasting seven hours till 2 p.m. This is also the period when medical specialists make their rounds. In the afternoon and evening, there are fewer nurses on duty. Things are quietening down for the night. There are also fewer deaths and emergencies, and fewer medical specialists present. During the night shift, everything is very quiet, there are few nurses on duty. There are also few events. Contrary to popular imagination, most people do not die in their sleep at night; they die in the morning while waking up.¹⁶

All this means that most nurses (especially full time, fully qualified nurses) spend many more hours on duty during the morning, and even less during the night, compared to the afternoon and evening. Most deaths occur (or at least, are registered to have occurred) in the morning. Therefore, most full-time, fully qualified nurses do experience many more deaths when they are on duty than occur when they are not on duty!

A complicating factor is that time of death has to be registered by a doctor. The rules on what a doctor is supposed to write on a death certificate vary in different jurisdictions: is it the time that they guess that the patient had died, or is it the time at which they sign off that they have determined that the patient has died?¹⁷ In some countries, data show that "official" times of death are often rounded to whole hours or whole half hours, sometimes even to whole days. A patient found dead in the morning might be registered as having died at five past midnight or at five past seven, for all kinds of innocent reasons.

¹⁴ Absence of evidence can sometimes be evidence of absence, see commentary of Aart de Vos, translated in Gill (2021), and Thompson & Scurich, 2018.

¹⁵ See Dotto, Gill & Mortera, 2022, especially Figs 2 and 3.

¹⁶ See Mitler, et al, 1987.

¹⁷ Currently in England and Wales there are no rules about this; in Scotland it is quite clearly codified at Scottish Government, 2018.

The activities of nurses can certainly influence these registered times. One might imagine that a better nurse checks up on all their patients more often and checks up more carefully and is more aware of how they are doing. A better nurse will therefore notice and signal a death (or an emergency) earlier than a worse nurse; thereby causing deaths to be registered in their shifts and not later. A better nurse will clock-in for work well before their shift starts, and clock-out well after it ends, in order to participate fully in the necessary hand-over from one shift to the next. There is a lot of evidence that the apparent excess of deaths when Lucia de Berk (see box over page) was on duty was connected to the fact that she was in fact a better (more hard working, more conscientious) nurse than many of her colleagues.¹⁸ In fact we know that she had been evaluated as an excellent nurse and consequently rapidly gained the necessary qualifications to be entrusted with harder tasks. The rapid increase in deaths on her ward coinciding with this “promotion” also coincided with a management decision to transfer babies with genetic birth defects from intensive care (where any deaths occur in different circumstances and are likely to be accurately recorded) to medium care, in order that they might then be rapidly transferred to home.

Notice that the nurses themselves, as well as their lawyers, or the experts they call as witnesses, may not think of these alternative hypotheses themselves. The same may be true of hospital authorities, who may be the first to sound the alarm and perform their own investigations, followed by police investigators and public prosecutors. Attention may then focus on the possibility that a suspected individual engaged in nefarious actions; the investigators may lack the knowledge or, in some instances the motivation, to identify possible alternative explanations.

There are additional examples of cases in which a cluster of deaths, initially attributed to individual misconduct, turned out to have another explanation. A cluster of deaths in a neo-natal ward in Toronto was initially associated with a nurse, who was suspected of malevolent activity. Only later was it discovered that new artificial latex products in feeding tubes and bottles could have been responsible.¹⁹ An apparent increase in death on a neonatal ward in England raised similar suspicions until a medical statistician identified the date at which the death rate rose, and a neonatologist recognized it as the date when the supplier of milk formula was changed. As these examples show, an increase in deaths may be caused by factors that are not immediately apparent, even to those involved. Such factors may require considerable expertise to discover and could be missed entirely in some instances.

¹⁸ See Gill, et al, 2018, Meester, et al., 2007 and Schneps & Colmez, 2013.

¹⁹ See Hamilton, 2011.

The case of Lucia de Berk

In 2003, Lucia de Berk, a Dutch paediatric nurse, was convicted of four murders and three attempted murders of children under her care. In 2004, after an appeal, she was convicted of seven murders and three attempted murders. Thereafter, several academic commentators questioned the quality of the evidence used to support the conviction, particularly statistical testimony.

De Berk had been under suspicion in her hospital for some months as a result of gossip about her tough, disturbed childhood and striking personality. When a child in her care died suddenly, the death was immediately announced to be completely unexpected and, by implication, suspicious. Hospital officials identified eight further deaths or resuscitations that had occurred while she had been on duty as medically suspicious. Additional suspicious deaths were identified and linked to de Berk at two other hospitals where she had worked. For two of the patients, investigators found toxicological evidence supporting the claim that de Berk had poisoned them, although the probative value of this evidence was weak. Statements in de Berk's diary about "a very great secret" and a "compulsion" on a day that a patient had died were given a sinister interpretation.

During her original trial, a criminologist (who had years earlier graduated in mathematics) presented statistical evidence according to which the probability of so many deaths occurring while de Berk was on duty was only 1 in 342 million. This number was the product of three p-values, one for each hospital. Prominent statisticians came forward to argue that the incriminating statistic was based on an over-simplified and unrealistic model, biased data collection, and a serious methodological error in combining p-values from independent statistical tests. The probability of so many deaths occurring by chance may have been as high as one in 25.

In light of these doubts, and further medical evidence that came to light in post-conviction investigations, the case was re-tried in 2010 and de Berk was acquitted. The original convictions are widely viewed as miscarriages of justice that were prompted, in part, by an inadequate investigation and misuse of statistical evidence. They led to various reforms in the Dutch legal system.

4. Investigative bias

Because criminal investigations are carried out by human beings, investigative findings may be influenced by common human tendencies (often called biases) that can affect the way investigators search for and evaluate evidence, as well as how they choose to report findings. This section will discuss ways that various widely recognised human biases may affect the investigation of misconduct by medical professionals, with a particular focus on how such biases may affect the statistical findings. The following section (Section 5) will discuss ways to minimise such biases to facilitate more objective and useful investigative outcomes.

a. Unconscious bias throughout society

Although a variety of specific biases have been identified,²⁰ they generally arise from a common phenomenon: that people’s expectations and desires can influence what they look for and how they evaluate what they find when they seek answers to important questions.²¹ The tendency of preconceptions and motives to influence people’s interpretation of evidence has been called “one of the most venerable ideas of ... traditional epistemology...” as well as “... one of the better demonstrated findings of twentieth-century psychology”.²² This tendency, which is often labelled an observer effect,²³ was mentioned in both classic texts and in the writings of early natural philosophers, such as Francis Bacon, who observed in 1620 that:

*The human understanding, when any proposition has once been laid down...forces everything else to add fresh support and confirmation; and although...instances may exist to the contrary, yet ...either does not observe or despises them.*²⁴

The potential for observer effects to distort scientific investigations was recognised by early astronomers, who discovered differences in reported findings of the same astronomical phenomena by different observers.²⁵ Historians of science have noted numerous additional ways in which human expectations or desires may explain incorrect reports of scientific observations, such as scientists’ failure to notice (or at least to report) phenomena inconsistent with their theory-based expectations; reported findings that support pet theories but cannot be replicated; and the statistically improbable degree of correspondence that has been observed between some reported findings and theoretical expectations (the most famous example from the history of science being the improbable degree of agreement between data and theory in Gregor Mendel’s experiments with peas).²⁶ Over the last 70 years, epidemiologists and statisticians have developed methods to limit and assess the impact of many of these biases.²⁷

The same scope for biased data collection has been noted in criminal investigations. Miscarriages of justice are often attributed to “tunnel vision” and “confirmation bias,” processes that may lead investigators to “focus on a particular conclusion and then filter all evidence in a case through the lens

²⁰ See Sackett, 1979, and Appendix D to The Law Commission, 2015.

²¹ Kassin, Dror & Kukucka, 2013; Thompson, 2009; Nickerson, 1998.

²² Nisbett & Ross, 1980.

²³ Risinger *et al*, 2003. For the relevance to epidemiological methods, see also Sackett, 1979.

²⁴ Bacon, 1620.

²⁵ Risinger *et al*, *ibid*.

²⁶ Pires & Branco, 2010; Jeng, 2006.

²⁷ Hill, 1965, is an early seminal reference. For approaches useful in forensic science, see Stoel *et al.*, 2015, Dror *et al.*, 2015.

provided by that conclusion.”²⁸ The comments of Findley and Scott on the underlying process are reminiscent of what Francis Bacon (quoted above) wrote in 1620:

*Through that filter, all information supporting the adopted conclusion is elevated in significance, viewed as consistent with the other evidence and deemed relevant and probative. Evidence inconsistent with the chosen theory is easily overlooked, or dismissed as irrelevant, incredible, or unreliable.*²⁹

Common investigative practices noted in the commentary by Findlay and Scott include tendencies for investigators:

- to settle too quickly on a preferred theory, without adequately considering alternatives;
- to look for evidence that confirms or supports the preferred theory rather than seeking evidence that might disconfirm it or support alternatives;
- to notice, remember and record evidence more readily and reliably when the evidence is consistent with the preferred theory than when it is not;
- to interpret ambiguous evidence in a manner consistent with the preferred theory;
- to view evidence and interpretations as more credible when they support the preferred theory, and *vice versa*;
- to report findings with a higher degree of confidence if they support rather than contradict the expected result;
- to fail to hand over or disclose all the countervailing evidence to the defence; and
- to have skewed incentives to boost their case.

A key part of any investigation is attempting to identify the full range of hypotheses that need to be explored, though it is difficult to be confident this is done successfully. Investigations can go awry, and produce misleading findings, if investigators miss or ignore an underlying causal factor. Deadly misconduct by a medical professional is one possible explanation for an unexpected surge in the death rate at a medical facility. Coincidence is another possible explanation (as discussed in Section 2(a)): clusters do occur by chance even in a completely random pattern of events. If investigators assume misconduct and coincidence are the only plausible explanations, then evidence indicating that coincidence is unlikely will lead investigators inevitably to the conclusion that misconduct is likely. This conclusion may be mistaken, however, if the elevated death rate arose, even in part, from other confounding factors, such as changes in the underlying population of patients; negligence or misconduct by other individuals; administrative changes affecting such matters as staffing levels, training, or case load; or medical policy changes affecting transfer of patients from one hospital section to another. See also the discussion on competing theories in Section 3.

The difficulty of identifying possible causal factors is multi-faceted.³⁰ It may arise in part from basic human psychological tendencies, as well as from self-interest of individuals involved. Psychological research suggests that people have a general tendency to gravitate toward criminality as an explanation for seemingly anomalous events, rather than looking at situational or institutional factors; this is called

²⁸ Findley and Scott, 2006, p. 292.

²⁹ Findley and Scott, *ibid.*

³⁰ The methods developed in medicine to bring together evidence from laboratory science, observational and experimental studies are important tools for investigation. In the UK, the Forensic Science Regulator has published advice on the development of evaluative reporting.

the “fundamental attribution error”.³¹ It causes people to look to the person (ie, to human agency) rather than the situation when explaining events. There is strong and well-demonstrated psychological tendency for people to assume that bad things are caused by bad people rather than bad circumstances (cf. the common public need to attribute blame to individuals, for “heads to roll”, in cases of systemic failure in public services).³² Hence, people may tend to look for scapegoats to blame for bad medical outcomes arising from other causes, and this is often encouraged by sensationalist reporting in the media.

The tendency toward scapegoating may be abetted by stereotyping and bias. Individuals accused of medical misconduct have often been unusual in ways that drew attention and ultimately suspicion, making the hypothesis of medical murder appear more plausible than otherwise. While it is important for investigators to take account of suspicious behaviour when that behaviour is diagnostic of misconduct, a focus on the odd-ball or iconoclast may unfairly distort investigators’ impressions of the matter if they mistakenly rely on stereotypes that have little probative value. Stereotypes with no empirical support, such as the notion that nurses whose fashion aesthetic tends toward the “gothic” are more likely than other nurses to commit murder, may draw unwarranted suspicion to certain individuals and make them investigative targets. People are not always conscious of the effect of such stereotypes on their thinking,³³ and through this unconscious bias, statistical evidence offered against a Goth nurse may be taken more seriously and examined less critically, than the same evidence would be if it were offered against a more conventional individual.

Cognitive biases can also affect the way that investigators interpret and classify data, and thereby distort the findings that emerge from an investigation. Epidemiological and statistical methods used in investigations of disease outbreaks or clusters of adverse events are applicable to investigating clusters of deaths.

Whether a particular death should be deemed “suspicious”, for example, might be influenced by a variety of factors, including factors that have little or no diagnostic value. Cognitive psychologists have found that people often have limited insight into the factors that influence such evaluations, so can be influenced by their own expectations or motives without realising it.³⁴ The largely unconscious nature of these processes makes the resulting biases difficult to remedy. Teaching people about such biases is not sufficient to prevent them, nor is exhorting people to be unbiased.³⁵ The most reliable and effective counter-measure is actively to avoid creating the biases in the first place by arranging, to the extent possible, to avoid creating strong expectations of desires for a particular outcome.³⁶ Additionally one needs proper checks and balances including “red-teaming” and independent stringent review of potential evidence, as done, for example, by the CPS in England and Wales.

b. Anatomy of a biased investigation

The general points about investigative bias offered in paragraph (a) above allow us now to consider more specifically ways that bias may distort the investigation of medical professionals accused of

³¹ Nisbett & Ross, 1980; Ross, 1977.

³² Burger, 1981; Ross, 1977.

³³ Nisbett & Wilson, 1977.

³⁴ Nisbett & Wilson, *ibid*.

³⁵ Kassin *et al.*, 2013; Risinger *et al.* 2003.

³⁶ Dror *et al.*, 2015.

harming patients. We will describe a hypothetical (but not completely fanciful) case in which a medical professional is accused of mass murder; we will then discuss how the cognitive tendencies discussed above may lead that investigation awry.

Let us suppose that administrators at a hospital become aware of an alarming increase in the number of deaths among elderly patients. Suspicion falls on a doctor who works in a unit where many deaths occurred. The doctor has drawn attention by speaking publicly in favour of euthanasia, making comments suggestive of relief rather than sadness after some patients died, and by appearing at the hospital's Halloween costume party dressed as the Angel of Death. When a co-worker reports seeing a syringe in the doctor's bag, hospital administrators call for an investigation.

At this stage, investigators often seek to determine whether the surge in deaths can be linked to the suspect. Were patients more likely to die when this doctor was on duty than when other doctors were on duty? To address this question, investigators often try to count the number of deaths for which the suspect may bear responsibility and compare it to the number of deaths that occurred under similar circumstances when the doctor could not have been involved.

In order to perform such an analysis, investigators must make a number of difficult judgments. They must determine, for example, whether each death that occurred should be viewed as a possible homicide, and if so whether the doctor in question could have been responsible for that homicide. Crucially, they must also consider whether factors other than the presence or absence of the doctor in question may have affected the rate of death.

Because there is a high degree of subjectivity in such judgments, they may be subject to bias. Furthermore, as we will explain, if the investigators are focused on a particular suspect, it is likely that these biases will slant the investigators' findings in a direction that is unfairly incriminating to that suspect. The remainder of this section will discuss ways bias may arise in an investigation; the following section will discuss possible ways to mitigate such biases.

c. "Suspicious deaths"

One important judgment is about which deaths to count. Investigators typically try to rule out deaths that are readily attributable to known causes and instead focus on deaths that are "suspicious" or "unexpected"—ie, deaths that might possibly have been the result of homicide rather than disease or other "natural causes." Distinguishing the former from the latter is a matter that requires expert judgment by specialists, such as forensic pathologists and researchers who study death certificate coding.³⁷ Research indicates, however, that forensic pathologists sometimes disagree about manner of death (eg, whether by homicide or accident) and that such judgments can be influenced by non-medical contextual information.³⁸ Post mortem evidence also confirms a high error rate in reported cause of death, even for good doctors.

For example, Dror et al recently reported that forensic pathologists who were asked to evaluate autopsy findings in a hypothetical case were more likely to conclude that a child died due to homicide rather than

³⁷ Ideally, forensic pathologists would be able to examine each corpse, but more realistically, death certificates should at least be reviewed by two people independently.

³⁸ For an example of the need to understand coding of deaths see the article on violent child deaths by Sidebotham et al, 2012.

accident if they were told it was a black child under the care of the mother's boyfriend than if told it was a white child under care of the child's grandmother.³⁹ Whether this finding reflects "bias" is controversial.⁴⁰ Some commentators have argued that information about the child and its caretaker is relevant to forensic pathologists' determination of manner of death and hence that it was perfectly proper for them to be influenced by it.⁴¹ Dror and his colleagues have argued in response that the information is beyond what forensic pathologists should consider when making such determinations and deserves little to no weight even if it is considered, and hence that their findings are indeed examples of "contextual bias".⁴²

For present purposes, the key finding of the Dror et al. study is that forensic pathologists' manner-of-death determinations can be influenced by contextual information, such as information about who was caring for the decedent. Let us consider how that might affect the fairness of the kinds of investigations we are discussing here. Suppose, for example, that a forensic pathologist is more likely to determine that a patient's death was "suspicious" and hence possibly due to homicide if aware that the patient was under the care of a suspected serial killer. This might happen because the forensic pathologist thinks it is proper and appropriate to consider such information when evaluating cause of death. Even if the forensic pathologist tries to ignore such information, however, it may still bias the evaluation by creating an expectation of homicide when the pathologist reviews cases associated with the suspected serial killer, and it may do so without the pathologist being aware of it.

Contextual information of this kind may also affect thresholds for reporting. Concern about missing possible victims may cause them to lower their threshold for reporting "possible homicide" when evaluating patients attended by the suspect; while concern about casting suspicion on an innocent person causes them to raise the reporting threshold for patients attended by other nurses. Consequently, when their evaluation of the medical evidence leaves them uncertain, forensic pathologists may be more likely to report a case as a possible homicide if they know the nurse on duty was a suspected serial killer, and less likely if another nurse was on duty.

Regardless of how it occurs, this kind of bias would undermine the fairness of the investigation by causing an increase in the count of "suspicious" deaths associated with the nurse. The higher count would arise from the very suspicions that the investigation is supposed to evaluate – an example of circular reasoning. Potential remedies for such biases will be discussed in Section 5.

d. Access and opportunity

Another important judgment that investigators must make is which suspicious deaths to count "against the suspect" (ie, as possible homicides committed by the suspect) and which to attribute to other causes. In order to make this determination, investigators need to evaluate, for each "suspicious death," whether the suspect had, or may have had, sufficient access to be responsible. That evaluation requires consideration of a number of factors, such as how the death may have been caused, how long it would have taken to perform acts that would cause the death, who else might have been present and whether

³⁹ Dror *et al.*, 2021a.

⁴⁰ Arguably, the experts were asked the wrong question: if they had been asked not about cause of death, but about likelihood ratios then context could be appropriately separated.

⁴¹ Peterson *et al.*, 2021.

⁴² Dror *et al.*, 2021b.

they would have observed and reported such misconduct, how soon thereafter the death would have occurred, how soon it would have been detected, and so on.

Like judgments about manner of death, judgments about access and opportunity to kill are complex subjective assessments on which different experts may have differing opinions (and, where experts are party-appointed, have implicit “advocacy-bias”).⁴³ Hence, they are also the kinds of judgments that may be influenced by contextual bias. There is a risk that investigators will be influenced by their expectations and desires. It is possible, for example, that they will cast a wider net when looking for “suspicious deaths” that can be linked to a suspect; and a narrower net when counting suspicious deaths that occurred when the suspect was not present. As a consequence, the deaths counted against the suspected individual could increase (relative to deaths counted against others) for the very reason that the suspect has come under suspicion.

e. Similar circumstances

To determine whether an unusual number of deaths occurred when a particular healthcare worker was on duty, it is necessary to compare the death rate when the worker was on duty with the death rate during ***otherwise comparable periods*** when the worker was not. It is often difficult to make such comparisons in a fair manner, however, because the presence or absence of the worker may be correlated with other factors that also affect the rate of death. In other words, the periods chosen for comparison may not afford a fair comparison with the periods when the worker was on duty.

Suppose, for example, that the worker typically works the morning shift. Investigators could compare the rate of deaths that occurred on mornings when the worker worked with the rate of deaths during the afternoon or night shifts on the same ward, but the result would be misleading if the rate of deaths is generally higher during the morning shift than during the other shifts. Investigators could instead compare the death rates on those mornings when the worker did and did not work, but that comparison may also be confounded by other factors. If the worker tended to work weekdays, for example, and not work weekends, it would be important to consider whether that factor (weekday vs. weekend) might also make a difference. Past investigations have sometimes compared rates of death during the period when a particular individual was on a medical staff with rates before or after. This kind of comparison confounds that presence and absence of the individual in question with the period of time, which could be misleading if time-related changes in procedure, staffing levels, patient population and the like might also have influenced death rates. Media reporting of poor outcomes in a hospital may deter future patients from seeking treatment there, changing the case mix and influencing future outcomes, and further confounding such comparisons.

Other factors affecting simplistic comparisons are the possibility of seasonal effects on disease prevalence and severity, and purely administrative matters such as the effects of hospital practice on recording of times of death, presence of doctors, shift changes, etc. In some hospitals, deaths occurring during a night shift are officially recorded only in the presence of a doctor at the beginning of the morning shift.

Investigators must carefully consider such factors in order to make a fair comparison. That will typically require considerable knowledge about factors that influence death rates, such as all those identified

⁴³ Murrie et al., 2013.

above. That suggests that investigators will either need to be knowledgeable medical professionals themselves or will need guidance from such professionals.

However, this guidance may itself introduce further biases, when it is obtained from administrators and staff of the institution being investigated. Then the officials who guide the investigation may have an interest in supporting particular outcomes, which could hinder the ability of investigators to identify the full range of possible causal factors. Suppose for example, that the increase in deaths that prompted the investigation arose after administrative changes that affected staff levels, training, or supervision. To avoid any implications of responsibility for a surge in deaths, the administrators may well prefer that the investigation focus on a single bad apple on the staff, rather than these background factors, and hence may de-emphasise or ignore them. This self-interested guidance may prevent investigators from recognising causal factors that confound their assessment of the rate of deaths attributable to a particular individual. It would be far better if the investigators had access to sophisticated guidance from experts on medical issues and hospital procedure who are independent of the staff and administration of the institution being investigated.

As in science, we should only compare like with like. When we cannot guarantee this by the design of the study, it is important to *control* for differences in other plausible causal factors.

In Appendix 5 we give two hypothetical examples that illustrate ways in which investigative bias may distort statistical evidence emerging from investigations of medical misconduct, emphasising that even very small biases can completely transform the strength of the evidence from weak to compelling. The second example also demonstrates that failure to control for differences in a causal factor can also lead to huge biases.

f. The role of chance

Throughout this report, we have recognised that the number of deaths observed while a particular medical professional is on duty is influenced by chance, in the form of natural sampling variation: comparing one period to another, the numbers of deaths will differ purely due to coincidence. Coincidental fluctuations from population means are more likely with smaller samples, where the law of large numbers does not dominate, than larger samples, hence there is a greater chance of observing an unrealistically high or low number of deaths for shorter intervals than for longer intervals, and for smaller patient populations than for larger ones. Calculations of statistical significance are precisely answering the question of whether observed differences between periods are greater than can reasonably be accommodated by these chance effects.

However, there are many other reasons why even in the absence of a causal effect of a medical professional's actions, numbers of deaths in different periods will differ. The behavioural aspects of these reasons have been grouped together by Kahneman into what he calls "noise".⁴⁴ This is really an umbrella term for quite different kinds of effect that we prefer to distinguish, as they require different treatments.

We have already discussed that other measurable factors such as season, time of day, etc., that differ between periods must be included in the analysis before effects can be attributed to particular causes, and we have illustrated how to do this. However, in addition, we have to accept the possibility of

⁴⁴ Kahneman, Sibony and Sunstein, 2021.

unmeasured confounders, the “unknown unknowns” we mentioned earlier. Statisticians often accommodate these factors probabilistically, for example, using random effect models, bringing a second role of chance into the situation, one for which the law of large numbers does not assist us (unless we are dealing with a large number of periods). A simpler approach is to allow for overdispersion in standard models, assuming for example “extra-Poisson variation”.

While the p -values presented in these examples take into account variability due to the size of the samples (ie, the number of cases examined), they do not, and cannot, take into account additional variability that may arise due to unmeasured variables. As discussed earlier, such factors may well increase or decrease the rate of deaths observed in actual cases. That means that bad luck (due to investigators’ failure to appreciate such factors) may increase the number of “suspicious deaths” that are counted against an innocent suspect in such an investigation, quite independently of the factors discussed in the hypothetical illustrations; and good luck (if that is the proper term) may decrease the number of deaths that are counted against a guilty suspect (if, for example, a killer happened to commit murders during periods when an unappreciated variable caused the death rate to be low).

5. Advice on investigative procedures

The foregoing analysis leads to three pieces of advice for professionals who are asked to investigate alleged misconduct by medical professionals. First, do not be oblivious to other factors that may affect the negative outcomes under investigation. Try to understand fully the factors that may have affected the rates of death or other negative outcomes that are at issue, and try to take all of those factors into account when assessing the likelihood that negative outcomes arose from misconduct by a particular individual.

Second, do not be biased, indeed take active steps not to be. Be familiar with the potential for cognitive bias and the subtle and often unconscious ways it can influence expert judgments, and take steps to minimise such biases. As explained below, that will typically require the lead investigators to establish context management procedures,⁴⁵ in order to control the flow of investigative information to other members of the investigative team. Failure to take such steps may permanently impair the investigators' efforts to produce findings that will be helpful, rather than misleading, to police, prosecutors and triers-of-fact.

Third, be cautious about drawing conclusions from limited samples, such as death rates over short periods of time. When examining rates of unexpected deaths (or other negative outcomes), seek the advice of statisticians on the appropriateness of the samples selected for evaluation, on ways to reduce sampling error and various forms of bias, and on the meaning and proper interpretation of statistical findings (in terms of both statistical significance and effect size, eg, relative risk).⁴⁶

a. Identifying all potential causal factors

A key part of any investigation is identifying the full range of hypotheses that need to be explored. As discussed in the previous section, investigations can go awry and produce misleading findings, if investigators miss or ignore an underlying causal factor. If an investigation is premised on the assumption that an unexpected set of patient deaths either resulted from intentional misconduct by a given individual or from coincidence, for example, then evidence that coincidence is unlikely will appear strongly incriminating. This conclusion may be misleading, however, if the elevated death rate arose, even in part, from other factors, such as:

- changes in the underlying population of patients,
- negligence or misconduct by other individuals,
- administrative changes affecting such matters as staffing levels, training, or case load, or
- changes in policy on moving patients between sections of the hospital.

Police are often called into such investigations by medical authorities who become suspicious of a given individual. The police may in turn rely upon those authorities to familiarise them with the situation and help them identify possible hypotheses in need of investigation. A danger inherent in this process is that medical authorities may have an interest in the outcome of the investigation that influences what they tell the police about possible causal factors. For example, faced with an upsurge in patient deaths, hospital administrators may find it easier to imagine that it was caused by individual misconduct of a “bad apple” on the staff than to acknowledge that it may have arisen from administrative decisions related to staffing

⁴⁵ See Dror et al., 2015; Stoel et al., 2015.

⁴⁶ Refer to Appendix 2.

and service levels; this may happen unconsciously. Identifying possible causal factors is a complex task requiring considerable expertise both in medicine and medical administration; it should not be left to amateurs, but also not left to parties involved in the matter.

Consequently, it is essential that investigators in such cases have guidance from experts who are independent of the institution being investigated. Because several types of expertise are relevant, it will often be necessary to have an advisory team or panel. To investigate a surge in deaths in the geriatric wing of a hospital, for example, investigators may need to consult experts in geriatric medicine, experts in forensic pathology and forensic toxicology, and experts familiar with hospital procedures, staffing practices and similar issues. The advisory panel should have sufficient expertise to identify every factor that might plausibly have contributed to the surge in deaths.⁴⁷ The advisory panel should also have the expertise needed to guide investigators on where to look for evidence that might support or undermine all plausible causal theories.

If the investigators attempt a statistical analysis, it is essential that they have guidance from a competent statistician. We discuss this further in paragraph (c) below.

b. Minimising bias

In 2009, the United States' National Academy of Sciences observed that "forensic science experts are vulnerable to cognitive and contextual bias" that "renders experts vulnerable to making erroneous identifications." (p.4 note 8). In the United Kingdom, the Forensic Science Regulator reached similar conclusions.

Support for these conclusions can be found in a growing body of research showing that forensic examiners can be influenced by contextual factors that are irrelevant to the scientific assessments they are supposed to be performing. For example, latent print examiners who were told that a suspect had a solid alibi were less likely to conclude that a latent print found at the crime scene had come from the suspect.⁴⁸ Similar findings have been reported in other forensic disciplines, including document examination,⁴⁹ bite mark analysis,⁵⁰ bloodstain pattern analysis,⁵¹ forensic anthropology⁵² and DNA analysis.⁵³

To minimise such biases, academic commentators and some advisory bodies have recommended that bench-level forensic scientists adopt context management procedures that shield them from exposure to potentially biasing contextual information that is not needed for their scientific analyses.⁵⁴ Generally, this requires dividing duties between a case manager and forensic examiners. The case manager

⁴⁷ Notice there may even remain "unknown unknowns". For example, with hospital baby deaths, nobody could have imagined that a change from rubber to plastic could have put digoxin-related substances into babies' bodies (see Hamilton, 2011). Of course, you can hardly take account of unknown unknowns quantitatively. But you should be aware that they are possible, and some statistical methods allow approximate adjustment for "unmeasured covariates".

⁴⁸ Dror, 2006; Dror & Charton, 2006; Dror & Rosenthal, 2008.

⁴⁹ Miller, 1984; Stoel, Dror & Miller, 2014.

⁵⁰ Osborne, Woods, Kieser & Zajac, 2014.

⁵¹ Taylor, Laber, Kish, Owens & Osborne, 2016.

⁵² Nakhaeizadeh, Dror & Morgan, 2013.

⁵³ Dror & Hampikian, 2011; Thompson, 2009.

⁵⁴ Dror et al., 2015; Thompson, 2015; Thompson, 2011; Risinger et al., 2002.

communicates with criminal investigators, determines what evidence needs to be collected and what examinations are necessary, and then passes the evidence on to forensic examiners, who evaluate the evidence and draw conclusions. The division of duties makes it possible for the case manager to be fully informed about underlying case and familiar with the context, while the examiner receives only the information needed to perform the analysis requested. In this manner the examiners can be “blind” to potentially biasing contextual information until after they have drawn conclusions. The fingerprint examiner does not learn, for example, whether the suspect has a solid alibi (or not) until after comparing the prints and drawing a conclusion. This procedure assures that the examiner’s conclusion is based solely on the analysis of the physical evidence submitted for examination and is not biased by other contextual information.

We recommend that a similar procedure be employed when investigating allegations of misconduct by medical professionals. A lead investigator could play a role similar to that of the case manager by communicating with other investigators and relevant authorities and identifying evidence in need of further examination. The lead investigator would be fully informed of the facts surrounding the case. The lead investigator would be supported by other individuals with specialised expertise who would conduct ancillary investigations. These ancillary investigators would not be fully informed about the underlying case but would deliberately be kept blind to information that is unnecessary to a fair scientific assessment, including the prior opinions and conclusions of other parties in the case.

Consider cases where a medical professional is suspected of killing patients by poisoning. It will likely be necessary to have toxicologists examine medical specimens to assess whether deaths that occurred during relevant periods could have been caused by poison. The toxicologists will need access to the specimens and will likely need information about the circumstances under which they were collected, but they need not know whether the specimens were collected from patients to whom the alleged killer had access, or from patients to whom the alleged killer did not have access. Information about access, although potentially biasing for reasons discussed in Section 4, is clearly irrelevant to the scientific analysis of the specimen. By keeping the toxicologists blind to this information, the lead investigator can greatly reduce the risk that contextual bias will distort the toxicological findings.

Lead investigators will typically need the assistance of forensic pathologists when assessing whether particular death should be regarded as “suspicious,” and hence as a potential homicide. As with toxicologists, however, the forensic pathologists need not be fully informed of all details of the investigation. When assessing whether a particular death was “suspicious” they should remain blind to whether the suspected medical professional had access to the deceased at least until after they have recorded their conclusions on cause and manner of death. Blinding will prevent the kinds of biases discussed in Section 4.

It is possible that some forensic pathologists will resist the use of blinding procedures that deprive them, even temporarily, of contextual information. Forensic pathologists in the United States have vociferously opposed the suggestion that they employ context management procedures in routine practice on grounds that the case context is always potentially relevant to their assessment of the medical history of the deceased and that no one other than a forensic pathologist has the competence to assess which parts of the case context may be medically relevant.⁵⁵ Additionally, forensic pathologists are accustomed to receiving all case information when they assess cause and manner of death for the purpose of issuing death certificates. For that purpose, they are expected to consider all the evidence surrounding the case

⁵⁵ See Simon, 2019.

that may bear on how the death occurred, including circumstantial evidence. Forensic pathologists might even consider it perfectly proper to take account of the fact that the deceased was under the care of a suspected serial killer when deciding whether to report the death as a homicide on the death certificate.

For reasons discussed in Section 4, however, in giving evidence to a court of law on the specific evidence in question in this kind of investigation, it is clearly improper for a forensic pathologist to be influenced by such information. As illustrated in the hypothetical examples, forensic pathologists may create an unfair bias against suspects if they allow such information to influence their judgments, and this undermines the fairness of the legal process. It is for the court to consider contextual information, such as that the deceased was under the care of a suspect, and the expert witness's assessment should be limited to the specific scientific evidence concerned; if this principle is not adhered to, there is a risk of "double-counting" of the contextual information when the court weighs all of the evidence, with prejudicial consequences. Biases of this kind are difficult to control because they can occur without conscious awareness. Simply instructing a forensic pathologist to ignore contextual information may well be insufficient; better practice would be to avoid exposing them to potentially biasing information until after they have made their assessment.

In summary, blinding is central to proper and defensible conclusions from analysis of numerical evidence. To promote its increased and widespread use in legal practice we recommend that it is adopted wherever practicable, that to encourage good practice its adoption is disclosed and indeed emphasised in court, and that if it is not practicable that reasons for this are explained.⁵⁶

In such investigations a little statistical knowledge may be a dangerous thing. Medical professionals or social scientists who have taken a few statistics courses may know how to compute statistics such as relative risk ratios and p -values, but may lack the sophistication and experience needed to do so in a manner that takes into account all relevant variables. The statisticians who advise such investigations should have three qualifications: (1) doctoral level training in statistics, ideally with an appropriate professional qualification (eg CStat in the UK); (2) experience with statistical analysis of medical data; and (3) familiarity with the academic literature on the investigation of misconduct by medical professionals, such as the literature cited herein, and this report itself. It is particularly important that statisticians advising such investigations be familiar with critical commentary that has identified flaws and limitations in previous investigations; the reference list contains a few examples. To improve the quality of future investigations, it is vital that investigators, and their advisors, treat past mistakes as opportunities for learning rather than defensively or for blame."⁵⁷

Some annotated examples of correct analyses of illustrative data on patterns of occurrence of adverse events are explained at length in Appendix 6, with explicit computer code to reproduce these in Appendix 8. These analyses make use of the standard statistical methodology of *log-linear models* (taught in the UK in many undergraduate courses).

⁵⁶ There is some evidence that the use of blinding procedures enhances the credibility of forensic evidence, particularly when the trier-of-fact appreciates that the evidence may depend, in part, on an expert's subjective judgments; Thompson & Scirich, 2019.

⁵⁷ See Matthew Syed, 2015.

c. The role for statistics in other specialist evidence

In this report we concentrate on cases where the data underlying the evidence in question consists of numbers of events, typically deaths. However, there is often a need for statistical interpretation of other kinds of data, typically presented by specialists of other disciplines, for example sciences such as toxicology or pathology, or social sciences such as criminology and forensic psychology.

In an investigation where conclusions drawn by specialists also involve data subject to any variation or uncertainty, a statistical analysis is necessary; it is important to have the opinion of a statistician about the soundness of that analysis. Scientific “intuition”, rules of thumb, “standard lab practice”, etc., are no substitute for an analysis that is correct. As the example in footnote 10 illustrates, intuition can be a poor guide in evaluating probabilities, especially regarding apparent “patterns” in irregular data.

For an example of a scientific analysis in a criminal case, it is common in cases where there is an unexpected number of deaths in a hospital ward that a pathologist is called to assess the cause of death. In the case of nurse Bolding, and others, the prosecution declared that potassium chloride was used by the suspect to kill a patient, on the basis of expert forensic pathologist evidence using earlier scientific studies that related potassium ion (K^+) concentration in the vitreous fluid of the eye to the post mortem interval (PMI). In a recent case the relationship between K^+ concentration and PMI was used to predict what the “standard” amount of K^+ should be at a certain (observed) PMI.⁵⁸ The patient had a higher concentration than predicted by the pathologist and the nurse was then accused of having injected the patient with potassium chloride, causing her death. In a first trial, this evidence was sufficient to convince the court to convict the nurse and sentence her to life imprisonment, but the analysis used to predict what the post-mortem potassium level should have been was flawed. Not only was the sample used to make the prediction not representative of the case under examination, but no measure of uncertainty was attached to the prediction. If a correct statistical analysis had been carried out the “incriminating” result would have been seen to lie within the “margin of error” – which means that the post-mortem analysis did not support the hypothesis that the dead patients had been injected with potassium chloride. The nurse was acquitted in a second trial in which a more complete statistical analysis was presented.

Likewise, any statistical analysis of data generated using other scientific disciplines should be accompanied by expert opinion in those disciplines.

⁵⁸ See Dotto, Gill and Mortera, 2022.

6. Advice for evidence evaluation and case presentation

a. The lawyer's role

Put starkly, a lawyer's role in an adversarial system is to advise and represent those who instruct them, to the best of their ability. Lawyers work (or ought to work) from facts to a solution. The advisory role requires an objective, independent evaluation of the evidence. Clients are ill-served if they are told only what they want to hear; others (including those accused of crimes) and the administration of justice itself may also be harmed by biased reasoning.⁵⁹ The representative role, however, is in essence the attempt to persuade the decision-maker (whether judge or jury) to make a finding favourable to the client on the evidence and argument, and within professional and ethical boundaries. The dividing line between persuasive and biased reasoning may be a fine one, and not always easy to identify; the potential harms of biased reasoning in a representative capacity are, however, self-evident and ought to be eliminated insofar as possible.

Both advisory and representative roles require an intimate knowledge of the facts and, where statistics are involved, the uses to be made and limits of such evidence. We suggest that the starting point ought to be a full, complete chronology (or thematic organization) of the facts; this is common practice in some area of law. Once that has been done, elementary strategies such as asking "what do we know?", "what don't we know?", and "what do we need to know?" ought to help to identify gaps, guide investigations, frame issues, and assist the building of argument.⁶⁰ If, once investigations are complete, gaps remain, then care ought to be taken not to fill them with speculation or (which may be the same thing) over-determined statistical analysis.

Even once the analysis is complete, there is still a place for sense-checking. Critical thinking techniques such as the "double standard test", the "outsider test", the "conformity test", and the "selective skeptic test" are likely to be useful in testing inference and argument.⁶¹

Courts in the UK have warned, at the highest level, that "there is a danger that so-called 'epidemiological evidence' will carry a false air of authority."⁶² The courts also recognise, however, that epidemiological evidence used with proper caution can be admissible and relevant *in conjunction with specific evidence related to individual circumstances and parties to a case*. The significance a court may attach to such evidence must depend on the nature of the epidemiological evidence, and of the particular factual issues before the court. The point was pithily made by Lord Rodger of Earlsferry that "Where there is

⁵⁹ In *The Scout Mindset*, Julia Galef describes biased, or directionally motivated reasoning as the "soldier mindset". By contrast, the reasoning underlying the "scout mindset" is motivated by accuracy.

⁶⁰ Amy E Herman, *Visual Intelligence*, pp153-164.

⁶¹ Julia Galef in *The Scout Mindset*, p71, describes these tests as follows:

- The Double Standards test is "Are you judging one person (or group) by a different standard than you would use for another person (or group)?"
- The Outsider test is "How would you evaluate this situation if it wasn't *your* situation?"
- The Conformity test is, "If other people no longer held this situation, would you still hold it?"
- The selective Sceptic test is "If this evidence supported the other side, how credible would you judge it to be?"

Other strategies are to be found in Tom Chatfield's *Critical Thinking*.

⁶² *Sienkiewicz v Greif (UK) Ltd* [2011] 2 AC 229 at p299, paragraph 206, per Lord Kerr of Tonaghmore JSC.

epidemiological evidence of association, the court should not proceed to find a causal relationship without further, non-statistical evidence”,⁶³ and by Baroness Hale of Richmond:

“The fact that there are twice as many blue as yellow taxis about on the roads may double the risk that, if I am run over by a taxi, it will be by a blue rather than a yellow one. It may make it easier to predict that, if I am run over by a taxi, it will be by a blue rather than a yellow one. But when I am actually run over it does not prove that it was a blue taxi rather than a yellow taxi which was responsible. Likewise, if I actually develop breast cancer, the fact that there is a statistically significant relationship between, say, age at first child-bearing and developing the disease does not mean that that is what caused me to do so.”⁶⁴

The criteria set out by Bradford Hill for inferring causality in epidemiological studies are also relevant here.⁶⁵

To properly advise their clients, frame the issues for the court, and present evidence and argument, lawyers need to (that is, should) understand and effectively deploy the statistical and epidemiological evidence and the inferences arising from them.

Evidence presented in a case at law can be regarded as data, and the issue to be decided by the court as a hypothesis under test. The relationship between these may be immediate, or else indirect, involving a long chain of intermediate propositions. The outcome of a criminal trial cannot be known in advance, as it requires sifting, evaluating, and deciding one or more issues; there is uncertainty about the relationship of the issue to the evidence such that there is a burden of proof. Such uncertainty can, in principle at least, be described probabilistically. We do not suggest that judges and juries are likely to have (or should be expected to acquire) a sophisticated understanding of probability or facility in manipulating probabilities; nor that explicit probability arguments should become routine in courts of law.⁶⁶ There are however increasing numbers of cases where evidence about probabilities is clearly relevant, and the court would stand to benefit from advice about how to handle them.

This section provides advice for lawyers and judges on how to deal with such cases when they reach the courts. As the previous sections have discussed, these cases are complex and can be extraordinarily difficult to investigate. If the investigations lead to prosecution, the evidence produced in court can be difficult to evaluate. In recent years, serious concerns have been raised about the fairness of the legal process in a number of these cases. Here are some suggestions about steps to take and pitfalls to avoid in order that these cases are tried fairly and justice is served.

⁶³ Also in *Sienkiewicz*, at p287, paragraph 163.

⁶⁴ *Sienkiewicz*, p290, paragraph 171.

⁶⁵ Hill, A. B., 1965.

⁶⁶ Although, in particular jurisdictions there may be relevant requirements for admissibility, eg in the USA, the Daubert standard for evaluating scientific evidence.

b. Evaluating event clusters

The first recommendation is to avoid giving undue weight to seemingly unlikely clusters of events. As discussed in Section 2, seemingly improbable clusters of events can arise by chance without criminal behaviour. Consequently, evidence involving event clusters may be less probative than people assume for distinguishing criminality from coincidence. Even if it is highly improbable that such a cluster would occur by coincidence, the best explanation might nevertheless be coincidence in the absence of convincing evidence to the contrary. Lawyers and judges should keep this point in mind. In jurisdictions that rely on lay juries, judicial instructions on this point may be helpful.

In the absence of other evidence, an unlikely cluster of evidence is difficult to evaluate and may be meaningless. When combined with other evidence, however, such events can be highly probative. Consequently, it is extremely important for triers of fact to consider whether evidence of an event cluster (eg, a surprising number of deaths among the patients of a particular medical professional) is supported by other more traditional evidence suggesting that the suspect had the motive, means and opportunity to kill patients. Failure to find such supportive evidence, when it would be expected, may constitute strong evidence against the theory that the suspected individual engaged in misconduct.⁶⁷ Judicial instructions on this point might also be helpful in some cases.

c. Recognising the consequences of investigative bias

A second recommendation is to be mindful of the dangers of investigative bias and the ways that it can unfairly bolster the apparent strength of the evidence. As discussed in Section 4, bias may arise from investigators' failure to consider all possible explanations for the deaths or other negative outcomes under investigation. Consequently, it is vitally important for lawyers, judges and jurors to consider carefully whether all potential causal factors have been considered. That will typically require expert assessments by individuals broadly knowledgeable about clinical medicine and clinical practice, and often other fields as well, such as epidemiology and statistics.

If it appears that the initial investigation may have been incomplete because investigators had insufficient access to independent expert advice or focused prematurely on an incomplete set of hypotheses, it is vital that independent experts be called upon to examine the evidence before trial. Courts should call such experts in jurisdictions where experts report to the courts, whether independent court appointed experts or single joint experts. In jurisdictions in which the parties typically provide courtroom experts, steps should be taken to assure that such experts are allowed and that parties can afford to provide them.⁶⁸

Courts should of course consider any alternative explanations offered by the individual under suspicion. It would be a mistake, however, to assume that the person under suspicion has sufficient knowledge or insight to identify all possible causal factors. During the trial of Dutch nurse Lucia de Berk (discussed in Section 3), who was convicted of murdering patients but later exonerated, the Judges asked de Berk whether she could explain why there had been so many deaths among her patients. They specifically

⁶⁷ See commentary of Aart de Vos, translated in Gill, 2021; Thompson & Scurich, 2018.

⁶⁸ We recognize, of course, that public resources are limited and that a balance must be struck between the needs of the parties for expert assistance and other priorities. Our goal is to explain the importance of expert assistance on this matter, not to comment on the priority it should receive relative to other needs.

asked her to comment on such matters as whether she lacked competence, whether her case load was more difficult, whether she had more night shifts. She could offer nothing to help her own case. Yet independent experts who examined her case after she was convicted identified a large number of potential causal factors that cast the case in an entirely different light, and ultimately contributed to de Berk's release from prison. The initial investigation had missed or ignored some of these factors, perhaps because they cast a negative light on individuals who were involved in the initial investigation. The Lucia de Berk case is thus an important cautionary tale about the need to involve independent experts before trial to avoid subsequent miscarriages of justice. Ideally this will occur during the initial investigation, but if not, then it needs to be done before the case comes to trial.

The fairness of the investigation may also be undermined by the failure of investigators to take adequate steps to mitigate contextual bias. As illustrated in Section 4, predictable biases may arise when experts assess such matters as whether a death was "suspicious" and whether the suspect had access to the decedent. Even if the effect of such biases on the number of deaths counted against the suspect is relatively small, the cumulative effect can be dramatic on statistics used to assess the significance of event clusters, such as p -values. Lawyers and judges need to understand that investigative bias can create seemingly powerful statistical evidence against someone who is entirely innocent. In light of that insight, they must consider whether adequate procedures were taken to control bias in the instant investigation and, if not, how that failure affects the probative value of the statistical evidence generated by the investigation.

A poorly conducted investigation may yield statistical findings that are so problematic that they do not warrant consideration. Jurisdictions that rely on lay juries as triers of fact often require judges to screen scientific testimony to assure it is sufficiently trustworthy to be admitted into evidence. In the United States, for example, Rule 702 of the Federal Rules of Evidence requires the trial judge to determine that proffered expert testimony "will help the trier of fact to understand the evidence," that it is "based on sufficient facts or data," that it is "the product of reliable principles and methods," and that the expert "has reliably applied the principles and methods to the facts of the case."⁶⁹ If the underlying investigation failed to consider relevant causal factors that might provide an alternative explanation for a cluster of deaths, and carried out the assessment linking the defendant to those deaths in a biased manner, it might well be appropriate for a judge to find that the resulting evidence does not meet the requirements of Rule 702 and should be excluded. Such evidence might also be subject to challenge under provisions such as Rule 403 of the Federal Rules of Evidence, which allows a trial judge to exclude evidence from consideration by a jury "if its probative value is substantially outweighed by a danger of ... unfair prejudice, confusing the issues, [or] misleading the jury ..."

Similar rules apply in England and Wales.⁷⁰ To assist the court, skilled (or expert) witnesses, unlike other witnesses, can give evidence of their opinions, if and only if they fall within their domain of proven and relevant expertise.⁷¹ If on the proven facts a judge or jury can form their own conclusions without help,

⁶⁹ The United States Supreme Court has addressed the admissibility of expert evidence under the Federal Rules in a series of cases that began with *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals* (1993) and included *General Electric v. Joiner* (1997) and *Kumho Tire v. Carmichael* (1999). All three cases emphasized the judge's role as a "gatekeeper" with the authority to exclude from the trial expert evidence that that is insufficiently "reliable" to be trustworthy.

⁷⁰ *Kennedy v Cordia Services LLP* 2016 SC (UKSC) 59, paragraphs [38] *et seq.*; see also *Forensic Science Regulator* (2015, 2021a, 2021b, 2022).

⁷¹ The Professor Meadows and shaken-baby syndrome cases, were cautionary examples of an expert straying outside their domain of expertise (medicine) and being also regarded by the court as expert in their non-expert opinion area (statistics).

then the opinion of an expert is unnecessary (and thus inadmissible).⁷² As with judicial or other opinions, what should carry weight is the quality of the expert's reasoning, not whether the expert's conclusions accord with other evidence. The expert should be careful to recognise, however, the need to avoid supplanting the court's role as the ultimate decision-maker on matters that are central to the outcome of the case. The expert's role is to provide information and analysis that is helpful to the trier-of-fact, not to comment directly on how the trier-of-fact should decide the case. On the question of impartiality and other duties of an expert, these include:

1. Expert evidence presented to the court should be, and should be seen to be, the independent product of the expert uninfluenced as to form or content by the exigencies of litigation.
2. An expert witness should provide independent assistance to the court by way of objective unbiased opinion in relation to matters within his or her expertise. An expert witness in the High Court should never assume the role of an advocate.
3. An expert witness should state the facts and assumptions on which the opinion is based, and should not omit to consider material facts which could detract from the concluded opinion.
4. An expert witness should make it clear when a particular question or issue falls outside his or her expertise.
5. If an expert's opinion is not properly researched because insufficient data is available, then this must be stated with an indication that the opinion is no more than a provisional one. In cases where an expert witness who has prepared a report could not assert that the report contained the truth, the whole truth and nothing but the truth without some qualification, that qualification should be stated in the report.
6. If, after exchange of reports, an expert witness changes his or her view on a material matter having read the other side's expert's report or for any other reason, such change of view should be communicated (through legal representatives) to the other side without delay and when appropriate to the court.
7. Where expert evidence refers to photographs, plans, calculations, analyses, measurements, survey reports or other similar documents, these must be provided to the opposite party at the same time as the exchange of reports.⁷³ This applies also to software.⁷⁴

In many jurisdictions, particularly those that use professional judges as triers of fact, there are no rules for exclusion of untrustworthy or unreliable scientific evidence. In those jurisdictions statistics generated in a poorly conducted investigation would need to be considered but could, of course, be dismissed or ignored if the judges found them unpersuasive.

While some investigations may be sufficiently problematic to justify excluding or ignoring the statistical findings entirely, courts are likely, in most cases, to treat investigative flaws, methodological limitations and potential biases as issues going to the weight of the evidence – that is, as issues for the trier of fact to consider when weighing the value of the evidence. In light of the issues discussed in this report, it should be clear that advice, reports and expert testimony from independent statisticians may be extremely important. If investigative bias is a significant concern, lawyers and courts should also

⁷² In the case of *Ben Geen*, see Gill RD, Fenton N, & Lagnado D (2022), the judge ruled that written opinions on the biasedness of the investigation submitted by two experts in the field of statistics and medicine was merely common sense. The experts were not allowed to present their opinions to the jury.

⁷³ *Kennedy*, p74, para [52], quoting from well-established case law.

⁷⁴ Similar best practice rules for experts are included in both the UK CPR Common Procedure Rules and various International Arbitration rules.

consider seeking evaluations from experts of cognitive bias and factors associated with the accuracy of expert judgment.

d. Avoiding fallacious interpretations of statistical findings

A third recommendation is to be mindful of the danger of drawing illogical conclusions from statistical findings, such as p -values, and to take steps to assure that misinterpretation of statistical findings does not undermine the fairness of the trial. As discussed in Section 2, people often transpose conditional probabilities, which can cause them to draw illogical and unwarranted conclusions from statistics like p -values, conclusions that may be quite unfair to an accused individual.

The first step in avoiding unfairness is for lawyers and judges to educate themselves about the proper interpretation of such statistics, so that they can avoid inadvertently incorporating such errors into arguments they make to the triers of facts or summations of evidence. It is also important that lawyers and judges avoid eliciting from experts testimony that incorporates or is conducive to such errors.

Avoiding error in the presentation of evidence is only the first step. Because people often jump to illogical conclusions on their own, it is not enough to present the evidence correctly. The trier of fact is likely to need guidance on correct interpretation of such statistics. If the triers of fact are professional judges, that guidance could be part of their professional training. Some jurisdictions are exploring the possibility of special education in probability for judges who will handle cases involving statistical evidence; such training would surely be appropriate for judges handling this class of cases.

With lay triers of fact, the guidance can take two forms. It could be incorporated into expert testimony. For example, experts could be asked to comment on the meaning of a p -value or similar statistic, which might allow them to identify incorrect interpretations. An expert might say, for example that a low p -value does not necessarily imply a low probability that the findings are coincidental. It means that the evidence observed is unlikely if coincidence is the underlying explanation, but coincidence may still be more likely than other explanations in the absence of convincing evidence supporting another explanation. In jurisdictions where judges instruct the jury on applying the law to the facts, guidance to this effect might also be incorporated into judge's instruction.

7. Conclusions and summary of recommendations

In this final section, we draw together our main recommendations. We reiterate that the scope of this report is the use of evidence based on statistical analysis in cases of suspected medical malpractice. Some of our recommendations may be appropriate in other contexts, but that is for others to say. We also recall that our scope is not limited to any particular jurisdiction; in some jurisdictions some of our recommendations may be redundant as they advocate what is already accepted practice.

It should be clear now that in our view, the statistical aspects of these cases are often nontrivial, fraught with difficulties, challenging to laypeople (jurors, media reporters, the public) and to lawyers. They are not entirely straightforward to the specialists!

- *Recommendation 1:* It is therefore important that all parties involved in investigation and prosecution in such cases consult with professional statisticians, and use only such appropriately qualified individuals as expert witnesses. [Section 5(c)]

There are two kinds of error in drawing inferences about effects from data: inferring an effect that is not real, or missing one that is. Both have grave effects in the judicial setting. It has been argued that if one decreases the error rate of one of the two kinds, the error rate of the other kind will go up; thus any change in practice shifts the balance between prosecutor and defence, shifting the errors from Type 1 to Type 2 or vice versa. That is only the case if nothing is changed in statistical methodology, apart from merely shifting a decision threshold. But one can reduce both error rates by increasing the amount of information extracted from the already available data, using superior statistical methods, and of course by acquiring more and different kinds of data.

- *Recommendation 2:* In presenting the results of statistical tests, both the level of statistical significance (p -value) and the estimated effect size should be stated. One addresses the question of whether an effect is truly *detected*, the other quantifies the *size* of that effect, if it exists. These are different concepts and both are important; neither should be confused with subjective judgements about the credibility of the expert witness. [Section 4(c), Section 5, and Appendix 2]

Special care is needed to assure that p -values, when presented in reports and testimony, are understood and used properly. While p -values are an important statistical and scientific tool, they are difficult for people to understand and are frequently misinterpreted. They may, for example, be misunderstood as statements about the probability that a coincidence occurred, rather than the probability of observing a given number of deaths (or more) by chance, and this kind of misinterpretation can be extremely unfair to individuals suspected of misconduct.

- *Recommendation 3:* In reports and testimony, experts should take care to explain the proper interpretation of p -values and should avoid drawing fallacious inferences from them. In jurisdictions that rely on lay jurors, judges should consider providing instructions about the proper use of p -values. Lawyers, judges and investigators should educate themselves to the dangers of fallacious statistical interpretation. Lawyers should endeavour to present the case in a manner conducive to correct understanding, avoiding to the extent possible testimony or arguments conducive to misinterpretations.

We have highlighted the importance of taking a broad and informed view of all the circumstances in which a cluster of adverse outcomes is observed, to ensure that all potential causal factors are identified,

and the problem that those best-informed may be implicated in alternative explanations for the data, with a consequent risk of bias. We therefore advocated that

- *Recommendation 4:* Investigations should be guided by panels representing all relevant areas of expertise but independent of both the suspect and the employing institution. [Section 5(a)]

Statistical investigations of the kind discussed here are not controlled experiments, but observational studies directed by humans, with all the inherent unconscious biases pervading all human reasoning. It is impossible to eliminate completely the role of human judgement in organising and conducting statistical data acquisition and analysis, but

- *Recommendation 5:* To the maximum extent practicable, experts informing an investigation, such as DNA specialists, fingerprint examiners, toxicologists, and pathologists should be kept “blind” to all aspects of the case irrelevant to the question they are being asked to answer. Blinding is a key tool in minimising prejudicial subjective effects such as unconscious bias. [Section 5(b)]

Guidelines of this nature for evidence of other kinds already exist in some jurisdictions. For example, organisations that issue practice guidelines for matters such as DNA evidence include SWGDAM (USA), FSR (England and Wales), ENFSI (Europe), and the International society of Forensic Genetics (ISFG; International).⁷⁵ Our recommendation for blinding is more comprehensive than what is currently required in most jurisdictions.

A second universal consequence of basing decisions about causes of effects on observational studies is captured by the well-known aphorism “correlation is not causation”.

- *Recommendation 6:* It is vital that investigators appreciate the truth of this, and the fact that the connection between them is well-studied, and that in fields such as medical diagnosis there are accepted criteria to guide the valid drawing of conclusions in observational studies [Section 6 and Appendix 7]. Possible confounding factors must be identified, and their effect quantified, before attributing causes to observed effects. [Sections 2, 4(a,c)]

This report is designed to promote stronger, more scientifically rigorous investigations of alleged medical misconduct. While that is the ideal, courts may still occasionally be called upon to evaluate evidence generated by poorly conducted investigations that produce problematic results. In jurisdictions that rely on lay juries as triers of fact, judges should consider whether the results of such an investigation are sufficiently reliable and trustworthy to meet legal standards for admissibility.

- *Recommendation 7:* When courts must evaluate the results of problematic investigations, it is particularly important that they consider reports and expert testimony from independent statisticians. If investigative bias is a significant concern, lawyers and courts should also consider seeking evaluations from experts of cognitive bias and factors associated with the accuracy of expert judgment.

⁷⁵ In England and Wales, the Forensic Science Regulator has issued Codes of Practice and Conduct for Forensic Science Providers and Practitioners, with recent proposed updates; see Forensic Science Regulator (2021b, 2022).

Understandably, most participants in the legal world have little training in matters of statistics and the scientific evaluation of uncertainty. In some countries, organisations in parts of the legal community ensure that training is available to those who would like it on probabilistic reasoning, statistical modelling, and statistical inference. In our opinion, defence lawyers first of all need to know that there is a whole scientific field out there which can help them serve their clients better. They need to be able to learn about the possibilities and to know how to find the professional community which can help them. Similarly, prosecution lawyers will need to learn about these matters – and if they do not, can expect cases built around inadequate statistical analysis to be successfully challenged by defence lawyers with aid of expert testimony. Judges too will need to be sufficiently informed to be able to determine admissibility and guide jurors accordingly. Not every legal professional needs to know everything: obviously, they cannot. However, within the different parts of the legal community, there do need to be people who do understand enough to know when professional support and further education is necessary. Our final, strong recommendation is therefore that

- *Recommendation 8:* Further interaction between legal and statistical communities should be fostered by the leaders of the legal and statistical communities, with a view to promoting joint educational activities.

Appendix 1: Probability and odds

The uncertainty of an event can be expressed quantitatively in several different ways. A probability is a number between 0 and 1, an impossible event having probability 0 and a certain one probability 1. For experiments that could be repeated indefinitely, the probability of an event can be interpreted as the proportion of times the event occurs in a very large number of independent trials. Another interpretation is the fair price in £ to buy or sell a bet that pays £1 if the event occurs and £0 if it does not.

Gamblers usually quantify uncertainty on a different scale, that of “odds”. In a race between 10 horses of equal ability so that the result is determined by chance, we would say that the odds on a particular horse winning were “9 to 1 against”, equal to a probability of $1/10 = 0.1$. In general the odds for an event of probability p are $(1/p)-1$ to 1 against, and the probability of an event for which the odds are O to 1 against is $1/(O+1)$.

In games between two unequal parties, say football teams, the odds against the weaker team winning might be quoted as 3 to 1, that is a probability of $1/4 = 0.25$. This is the same as saying that the stronger team has odds of 3 to 1 “on” or “in favour of” winning (the possibility of a draw is being neglected here). These are all ways of suggesting that in a long run of games between the teams, the stronger team would win 3 times as many as the weaker. Bookmakers have to make a living, so these numbers are different from those offered when inviting bets, of course.

There are many different traditions across cultures and countries for expressing odds verbally or typographically; to avoid ambiguity it is important to be clear whether the odds quoted are “against” or “in favour of”, and not to simply state, eg, “the odds are 5”.

Appendix 2: Statistical significance, effect size and risk

It is important to be clear about the distinction between absolute and relative risk, and the role of statistical significance in reporting changes in risk. These issues are discussed in standard textbooks, so we just give a brief summary here, and set this summary in the simplest possible context of a “before/after” comparison. Before an intervention (for example, the appointment of a new nurse), we observe a certain proportion of adverse outcomes (for example, unexplained deaths of patients); after that intervention, we see a higher proportion – how should we interpret this? We assume here that there are no other changes in circumstances; in Sections 3 and 4 we discuss at length reasons for caution in making this assumption.

First, statistical significance – in contrast to what we might call scientific significance or importance – is simply a statement about a p -value. Recall that a p -value is the probability that the data would show a change as large as that observed, or more, under the assumption (the “null hypothesis”) that there is no causal effect of the intervention – the difference is just due to chance, the nurse is innocent of wrongdoing. If the p -value is very small, we would be so surprised to see these data that we prefer to disbelieve the null hypothesis; if it is large, we will conclude that the evidence from the data is inconclusive, we accept that chance is a plausible explanation.

To help convey this interpretation of the p -value verbally, in many disciplines we use the idea of “statistical significance”. A result is typically termed “statistically significant” if the p -value is less than 0.05 (5%); sometimes for emphasis we write “statistically significant at the 5% level”. Commonly, the terms “highly statistically significant” or “very highly statistically significant” are used if the p -value is less than 0.01 (1%), or 0.001 (one in a thousand) respectively, but these terms are not universal. It is usually considered good practice now to simply report the numerical p -value.

As already stated, statistical significance is not the same as real-world importance, it is simply a statement about whether the results could be explained by chance. We quantify importance in the idea of “effect size”. This is measured in different ways in different kinds of analysis; for our before/after study we would typically quantify effect size using relative risk or difference in absolute risk. If the proportion of adverse events increased from 0.04 to 0.06, this could be reported as a relative risk of 1.50, or an increase in absolute risk of 0.02. These two statements mean exactly the same thing, but there is an evident possibility of their being interpreted differently by the casual reader, and evident opportunities for sensationalising changes by choice of presentation – especially when expressed as percentages. Is this a 50% change (in relative risk, from 1.00 to 1.50), or a 2% change (in absolute risk, from 4% to 6%)?

There is no general relationship between statistical significance and effect size. While it is true that within the context of a single study on a fixed number of subjects, p -values go down as effect sizes go up, there are no other implications. Table 1 below illustrates this. Comparing cases (a) and (b) we see that a given effect size in a small study may not be statistically significant, while the same effect size in a large study would be, another consequence of the fact that in small samples the law of large numbers does not dominate, as discussed in Section 4(f). Comparing (b) with (c) and (d), we see that for rare events, changes appear greater if expressed using relative risks, and that for a given relative risk, a rare event is less statistically significant. Finally, studying (c), we see that even with 800 patients considered, a doubling of the risk from 5/400 to 10/400 is not statistically significant.

Table 1 Comparing p -values, and absolute and relative risks for 4 artificial data sets, tabulated below

Case	p -value	Relative risk	Absolute risk difference
a	0.15	2.00	0.125
b	0.000006	2.00	0.125
c	0.19	2.00	0.0125
d	$<10^{10}$	11.00	0.125

	Case (a)	
Outcome	Before	After
Adverse	5	10
Normal	35	30

	Case (b)	
Outcome	Before	After
Adverse	50	100
Normal	350	300

	Case (c)	
Outcome	Before	After
Adverse	5	10
Normal	395	390

	Case (d)	
Outcome	Before	After
Adverse	5	55
Normal	395	345

Appendix 3: Sensitivity and specificity

In testing a binary, true/false, statement, two kinds of errors can be made – to decide true when it should be false, or false when it should be true. Particularly in medical testing, we use the terms sensitivity and specificity to quantify how well the test avoids these two kinds of error. The probability of getting a positive test result on a patient who does have the disease is called the *sensitivity*; the probability of getting a negative test result on a patient who does not have the disease is called the *specificity*. Ideally both should be near to 1 (100%). It is not meaningful to speak of the “accuracy” of a test: the proportion of patients whose test give the “right” answer depends on the disease prevalence. Bayes’ rule evaluates this probability.

Appendix 4: Bayes' rule

To illustrate how to avoid the Prosecutor's Fallacy, and correctly "invert the conditional" to calculate the probability of the hypothesis given the evidence, let us start by considering a different example in detail. The approach we describe will allow the proper quantitative comparison of competing explanations for the data at hand.

Testing for a disease

Suppose we are trying to determine whether a medical patient has a particular disease after learning that the patient had a positive test result for that disease. Let us suppose that two kinds of evidence are available: evidence about the prevalence of the disease among people like the patient, and evidence about the accuracy of the diagnostic test. Assume the test correctly shows positive results for 9 out of 10 people who have the disease, but produces false positive results for 1 person in 100 who does not have the disease. What is the probability that our patient, who had a positive test result, has the disease?⁷⁶

Because there is only 1 chance in 100 that the patient will have a positive test result *if* the patient does not have the disease, it might be tempting to assume that there is 1 chance in 100 the patient does not have the disease and, therefore, 99 chances in 100 that she does have the disease. By now, however, readers should be sceptical of this logic. As we have explained, the probability of A given B is not necessarily the same as the probability of B given A. But what conclusions can be drawn?

To draw conclusions, we must consider the test result in connection with other evidence – in this case, information about the prevalence of the disease among people like the patient. Let's assume that it is a rare disease found in only 1 person in 1,000 in people like the patient. With this additional information, we can draw conclusions, as laid out in the following paragraph, and depicted in Figure 1 and Table 2.

Consider 1 million people like this patient. If 1 in 1,000 have the disease, we would expect there to be 1,000 who have it and 999,000 who do not have it. So the overall chances of having this disease among people like our patient will be 1 in 1,000. The diagnostic test greatly shrinks the group without the disease, however, by eliminating the 99% of them who give a negative test result. Among the 999,000 who do not have the disease, only 9,990 will give a positive test result. Because the test also produces a positive result for 9 out of 10 people who do have the disease, we would expect 900 of the 1,000 people who have the disease to give a positive test result, so altogether there will be $9,990 + 900 = 10,890$ positive results. But notice that that means there will be more positive test results among people who do NOT have the disease (9,990) than among people who do have the disease (900). So the chances that a person with a positive test result actually has the disease is only $900/10,890$ or about 1 in 12. These calculations are illustrated in Figure 1 and Table 2.

The positive test result has certainly helped assessment of the patient. Before knowing the test result, the odds were 999:1 against the patient having the disease; after learning of the positive test result, the odds have shortened considerably to about 11.1 against. (The relationship between probability and odds is elaborated in Appendix 1). The test result seems highly indicative of disease. Nevertheless, when

⁷⁶ Over the course of the Covid pandemic, most readers will have become very familiar with situations like this, and the interplay between population prevalence, and sensitivity and specificity of different types of test. See also Appendix 3.

considered in light of the other evidence, the odds are still against the patient having the disease, even after learning of the positive test result.

Figure 1 A simple numerical example of Bayes' rule

Table 2 A simple numerical example of Bayes' rule

	Population (prior)	After positive test (posterior)	After negative test
No Disease	999,000	9,990	989,010
Disease	1,000	900	100
Total	1,000,000	10,890	989,110
Chances of having disease	1 in 1,000	1 in 12.1	
Odds against having the disease	999 to 1	11.1 to 1	

The shift in odds described in the previous paragraph can be computed more quickly by multiplying the prior odds against the disease, 999,000 to 1,000, ie 999 to 1, by what statisticians call the likelihood ratio: the ratio of the probabilities of a positive result among the ill and the well, 90% divided by 1% ie 90. This approach is quite general, and is known as Bayes' rule:

$$\text{POSTERIOR ODDS} = \text{PRIOR ODDS} \times \text{LIKELIHOOD RATIO.}$$

Later we will explain this reasoning in a more mathematical notation and in a more general context. Bayes' rule is of course quantitative, but it is also profitable to understand it qualitatively. On the face of it, the imperfections in the test do not seem to invalidate it: there is only a small chance of a false positive, and its usefulness seems nicely captured by the reassuringly large likelihood ratio, 90. The

likelihood ratio is the ratio of the probabilities of the observed data under the two hypotheses considered, and is often abbreviated as LR. However, the test is very poor when used like this in a situation of low disease prevalence, as we see that a citizen testing positive is over 11 times more likely to be well than ill. The apparent evidence in favour of the disease from a positive test result is completely outweighed by the prior odds that the citizen tested is well. To detect a rare disease successfully, we need a very much smaller false positive rate (that is, improved *specificity*).⁷⁷

Suspected serial homicide

Now let us consider how this analysis might apply to a case of suspected serial homicide by a medical professional. The p -value is analogous to the false positive rate of the diagnostic test – it tells us how likely it is to get “positive evidence” (a given number of deaths) if the suspect is not guilty, and the cluster of deaths arose by coincidence and hence informs us regarding the likelihood ratio. By itself, the p -value cannot tell us the probability the suspect is guilty or not guilty. But it can provide insight into how much our assessment of guilt should change in light of the cluster of deaths. Whether the posterior odds will favour coincidence or misconduct will depend partly on what other evidence suggests about the “prior odds” and partly on the strength of the likelihood ratio.

To summarise, while unexpected clusters of deaths, or other adverse outcomes, may raise legitimate suspicions and warrant further investigation, they generally should not be taken as definitive evidence of misconduct. And this is true even if we accept two key assumptions underlying the analysis we have just presented, assumptions that may be problematic in other instances: (1) that the only plausible explanations for what happened are misconduct by a particular individual and an extremely unlikely coincidence; and (2) that there is a sound scientific basis for the probabilities that underlie the LR.

The general case

Finally, we give a brief more technical discussion of Bayes’ rule. As an illustration in a case of medical misconduct, let H_p be the (prosecution) hypothesis that a medical professional engaged in misconduct that placed his/her patients at an elevated risk of death. Let H_d be the defence hypothesis that no such misconduct took place, and hence the risk of death to the patients is the same that would be expected for other similarly situated patients. Let E be the evidence considered in this case – a specific number of deaths in a given period in a given ward when the medical professional is on duty. The adjudicator needs to assess the conditional probability for either hypothesis, given the evidence: $P(H_d|E)$ and $P(H_p|E)$. It will not usually be possible to assess these directly, however it will often be reasonable to assess the probability that the evidence would have arisen, under each of the competing scenarios: $P(E|H_d)$ and $P(E|H_p)$, ie the probability of the evidence E given the defence hypothesis and given the prosecution hypothesis. Recall that the p -value is not the same as the probability of the evidence E given the defence hypothesis $P(E|H_d)$, but it is the probability of the evidence and more extreme evidence given H_d .

⁷⁷ As the 18th century French mathematician Pierre-Simon Laplace wrote: *We are so far from knowing all the agents of nature and their diverse modes of action that it would not be philosophical to deny phenomena solely because they are inexplicable in the actual state of our knowledge. But we ought to examine them with an attention all the more scrupulous as it appears more difficult to admit them.* Paraphrased by Carl Sagan as *The weight of evidence for an extraordinary claim must be proportioned to its strangeness.* See Tressoldi, *Frontiers of Psychology*, 2, 117.

What investigators/judges/juries want to know is the probability the prosecution hypothesis H_p is true in light of the evidence. *Bayes' rule*, a trivial consequence of the definition of conditional probability, tells us that

$$\frac{P(H_p|E)}{P(H_d|E)} = \frac{P(H_p)}{P(H_d)} \times \frac{P(E|H_p)}{P(E|H_d)} \quad (1)$$

The posterior odds for comparing H_p and H_d , given the evidence E is a simple transformation of $P(H_p|E)$, the desired posterior probability of H_p , *ie* that the suspect engaged in misconduct. It is important to note that this formulations of Bayes' rule using odds remains valid whether or not the hypotheses H_p and H_d are mutually exhaustive; it is not necessary that their probabilities add to 1. The "odds" above are all for one hypothesis (H_p) relative to another (H_d).

The second term on the right-hand side of (1) is constructed out of the directly assessed terms $P(E|H_d)$ and $P(E|H_p)$: it is the likelihood ratio (LR) for H_p as against H_d , engendered by the evidence E . It is noteworthy that only the ratio of these terms enters, their absolute values being otherwise irrelevant. The first term right-hand side of (1) $P(H_p)/P(H_d)$ is the prior odds for comparing H_p and H_d (*ie*, before the evidence E regarding a high mortality rate is incorporated). The prior odds might reasonably vary from one individual adjudicator to another.

When E denotes all the evidence in the case, all the probabilities in (1) are unconditional; in particular, the prior odds should be assessed on the basis that there is no evidence to distinguish the suspect from any other potential suspect - this can be regarded as one way of formalising the legal doctrine of "presumption of innocence" (which of course is not the same as an assumption of innocence). When E denotes a piece of evidence presented in mid-process, all the probabilities in (1) must be conditioned on the evidence previously presented: in particular, the "prior" probabilities could themselves have been calculated using (1), as posterior probabilities based on earlier evidence.

Appendix 5: Cumulative effects of bias: two worked numerical examples

To illustrate ways in which investigative bias may distort statistical evidence emerging from investigations of medical misconduct, let us consider the following hypothetical examples.

Example 1

First, imagine a hospital ward where 1000 patients are treated per year and where the annual death rate has historically been 10%. In a given year, however, the death rate doubles due to a variety of factors. For example, the increase in deaths might have been really caused by

- changes in the patient population that increased the number of sicker, older patients;
- changes in staffing that affected the quality of care, such as reduced staffing levels, loss of better qualified staff members, reduced training, lower morale;
- changes in administrative procedures that reduced monitoring, or error checking;
- counter-productive changes in treatment regimens, or
- some combination of such factors.

Suppose that hospital administrators, alarmed at the sudden increase in the death rate, look for an explanation and focus their attention on a nurse who was hired just before the death rates increased. Perhaps the nurse has eccentric qualities or manifests eccentric behaviour, such as laughing or making jokes when a patient dies, drawing colleagues' attention. To investigate the possibility that this nurse is causing patients to die, they seek to determine whether the nurse can be linked to "suspicious deaths" that occurred on the ward.

One approach would be to compare the number of "suspicious deaths" before and after this nurse was hired. Let's suppose that a fair and unbiased investigation would classify 10% of the deaths that occurred as "suspicious"—that is, as deaths that could possibly have been due to homicide. Assuming the nurse in question is completely innocent, and murdered no one, the result of the investigation would be 10 "suspicious deaths" among 1000 patients before the nurse was hired, and 20 in the year after hiring. This finding looks a little incriminating, although the increase is not statistically significant at the 5% level (see Table 3) even if no other factors were at play.⁷⁸ The "relative risk ratio," as calculated by investigators has doubled after the nurse was hired. But the nurse had nothing to do with it: the increase was caused entirely by factors related to patient population, staffing and supervision—factors that investigators may fail to consider while focused on the hypothesis that the causal factor was the nurse.

Now let us suppose that the investigation is not fair and unbiased, but is instead slanted toward incriminating findings due to the investigators' unconscious cognitive biases. Suppose, for example, that the rate at which the experts deem deaths to be suspicious increases from 10% to 15% when they are told that the death occurred while an alleged serial killer was "on duty," and decreases to 5% when they are told the death occurred during the alleged killer was not "on duty." Under those assumptions, 30 "suspicious deaths" would be reported during the period after the suspected nurse was hired and only 5

⁷⁸ Appendix 8 details how this, and other, calculations of p -values were performed.

in the period before, for a “relative risk ratio” of 6 (see Table 3). In other words, it now appears that suspicious deaths were six times more likely after the nurse joined the hospital staff than before. The p -value, indicating the probability of this difference occurring by chance is about 0.0068 (about 1 chance in 150), which sounds strongly incriminating for the nurse. But of course, the nurse is entirely innocent. The seemingly incriminating finding was generated by biased investigators who failed to take account of other factors that might have affected the death rate and interpreted the data in a manner that was inadvertently influenced by predictable human biases. An unbiased investigation would have shown a smaller (and therefore less incriminating) increase in deaths.

Table 3 Number of “Suspicious Deaths” Before and After Suspect Joined the Hospital Staff (as Reported by a Biased Investigation)

	Patients	Deaths	Deaths Deemed “Suspicious” in a Biased Investigation	Deaths Deemed “Suspicious” in an Unbiased Investigation
Before	1,000	100	5	10
After	1,000	200	30	20
Relative risk ratio			6	2
p -value ⁷⁹			0.0068	0.5876

Example 2

Another approach that investigators may take is to compare the number of “suspicious deaths” when the nurse was or was not on duty. Our second example illustrates how statistics produced by such comparisons can be distorted by (a) failure to take account of other causal factors that may correlate with the duty periods; and (b) investigative bias in determining which deaths are suspicious. It also allows the time periods over which the data are collected to be unequal in length.

Suppose that 16 patients die in circumstances assessed by investigators to be suspicious over a 15-day period on the ward in question, with 9 of those deaths reported during the 7-hour morning shifts and the remaining 7 during the afternoon and night shifts. The nurse under suspicion works 8 morning shifts, and 2 of the afternoon or night shifts. So the raw rate of suspicious deaths tends to be higher when the nurse is on duty than when not, simply by virtue of the nurse’s pattern of work. The first columns in Table 4 (under ‘Unbiased investigation’) tabulate these values. Compared to Example 1 it is now more difficult to interpret the data intuitively, but cross-classifying the deaths by shift and the nurse’s presence in this way suggests that the time of day is an important factor; an appropriate formal method of analysis is described in Section 5(c) below, and yields the p -values in the final line of the table. These show that allowing for the inherent differences between shifts transforms the strength of evidence against the nurse from statistically significant ($p=0.017$) to very weak indeed ($p=0.378$).

⁷⁹ p -values computed using (one-sided) Fisher’s exact test.

Table 4 Numbers of “suspicious deaths” when suspect was and was not on duty, under assumptions of both unbiased and biased investigations (see text)

		Deaths attributed to nurse on duty			
		Unbiased investigation		Biased investigation	
	Shifts	Ignoring morning effect	Allowing for morning effect	Ignoring morning effect	Allowing for morning effect
Nurse on duty, morning	8	10	7	12	8
Nurse on duty, other ⁸⁰	7		3		4
Nurse off duty, morning	2	6	2	4	1
Nurse off duty, other	28		4		3
<i>p</i> -value ⁸¹ for nurse effect		0.017	0.378	0.0007	0.031

Finally, let us suppose that cognitive bias also influences the investigators’ assessments of whether each of the deaths was suspicious, in such a way that 2 additional deaths during the nurse’s shifts are now judged suspicious, one in the morning and one in the afternoon, while one fewer death was called suspicious in each of the counts where the nurse was not on duty. The final columns of Table 4 (under ‘biased investigation’) show these data, and the corresponding *p*-values, show that this small bias (which might also have been caused by simple mis-recording in duty records) is enough to make the evidence now statistically significant ($p=0.031$) even when we assume there is no difference between morning and other shifts in mean rates of death, whilst if we do not allow for such differences the evidence is very highly significant ($p=0.0007$).

All of the analyses here assume that there are no other causal effects, such as seasonal factors or administrative changes, that need to be taken into account.

In Appendix 6, we describe analyses of the data in these two examples, and explain the logic and the calculations that lead to the *p*-values quoted above.

⁸⁰ i.e. afternoon, evening or night shift

⁸¹ Using likelihood ratio test for equality of rates, with and without adjustment for morning effect. This is the chi-squared test conventionally used in the analysis of deviance; see Appendix 6.

Appendix 6: Patterns of occurrence of adverse events

Here we give some annotated examples of correct analyses of illustrative data on patterns of occurrence of adverse events. To simplify exposition we will write about unexpected deaths of patients in a section of a hospital, and take the “explanation” under consideration to be deliberate harm caused by a nurse. Of course, this exposition applies *mutatis mutandis* to many other scenarios, and any professional role, etc.

We will assume that these events occur completely at random, but at a rate per unit of time (hour, shift, day, etc., as appropriate) that varies with time, and may be influenced by factors of the kind already discussed: seasonal and diurnal effects of disease, administrative changes, etc., and also, possibly, by wilful harm. We use the phrase “completely at random” in its proper mathematical sense, to mean that the occurrence of an event at a particular time has no direct influence on the time of any other event. (In other words, we consider only *exogenous* causes for the variation in rate of the adverse event, not *endogenous* ones). This rules out for example infections of a contagious disease, where there can be a direct causal link, but would cover heart attacks. The only other assumption we make is that when we consider two or more causal factors for the variation in rate, the effects of these are multiplicative: the percentage change in rate when one factor is present is the same whether or not other factors are also present.

As an artificially simple example, consider a hospital ward which is staffed either by nurse A or by nurse B. Numbers of deaths when each of the nurses is in charge are counted, and summarised here:

Table 5 Illustrative example: patient survival statistics under the care of two nurses

	Nurse A	Nurse B	Total
Died	15	9	24
Survived	25	31	56
Total	40	40	80

Could the apparent discrepancy in rates of death be attributed to chance, “just a coincidence”? We suppose that all circumstances of the Nurse A and Nurse B shifts are identical; there is no other conceivable reason for the apparent difference other than the presence of one nurse or the other.

This data structure is called a (2 by 2) contingency table: the standard way to analyse this, to test the hypothesis that there is no difference in the death rates attributable to the nurses, is “Pearson’s chi-squared test”. This is an elementary technique, taught in the middle years of high school (eg GCSE level in England and Wales). This reveals that the probability of observing a difference in apparent death rates as large as, or larger than, that seen in the table, *if there was really no difference* is 14% (that is the *p*-value is 0.14). That means that if you were to repeatedly allocate 24 deaths and 56 survivals into two groups of 40 patients at random, a difference in apparent rates as large as that in Table 5 would be obtained about 1 time in 7. We have to conclude *there is no significant difference*. It would be misleading to the court to testify that there *was* a difference. A *p*-value less than 0.05 is a pre-requisite for publication in the scientific literature (and this is not a tough standard, very many scientific “findings” are never replicated by other scientists).

The *p*-value above is calculated as follows. Since 24 out of the 80 patients die, if there were no nurse differences, you would expect that (24/80) of 40, ie 12, of the deaths would occur on Nurse A’s shift. In the same way, for each of the other counts in the table (9, 25 and 31) you would expect respectively (12,

28 and 28). We denote the observed numbers (15, 9, 25, 31) by O_i and the expected numbers (12, 12, 28, 28) by E_i , then calculate

$$G = \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i},$$

(that is, we take each of the cells of the table in turn and square the difference between the observed and expected numbers, and divide by the expected number; these fractions are added up over the four cells), which is 2.143. To convert this to the p -value quoted, we can use standard printed tables of the chi-squared distribution, or the function found on many calculators and all statistical software packages.

In contrast, if all of the numbers in Table 5 were exactly 10 times larger (150, 90, and so on), then the Pearson chi-squared statistic G would be 21.43 and the p -value turns out to be 0.000004, so there would be overwhelming evidence that the apparent difference in death rate was *not* due to chance. (This is an example of the point made in Section 4(f) that “coincidental fluctuations from population means are more likely with small samples...”).⁸²

Contingency tables of any size, not just 2 by 2, can be analysed with Pearson’s chi-squared test, but still very few criminal cases are simple enough to fit into this setting. Nevertheless, the analysis can be extended to deal with much more complex situations, allowing in particular more than one causal factor, and different durations of time. The more general framework is that of *Poisson log-linear models*, which are an example of *generalised linear models*. This is also a standard methodology, but one now taught not at high school but in undergraduate courses in mathematics and statistics. When applied to a 2-way contingency table, the results are the same.

These methods are provided in standard statistics packages, and will be part of the toolbox of all practicing professional statisticians. The assumptions underlying their use are simply those mentioned above, and courts should be able to accept results of such analyses in expert witness testimony, just as, for example, a scientist would expect to be able to present scientific evidence relying on data from electron microscopes or mass-spectrometers without needing to explain to judge and jury the physics needed to say how these complex machines function. In short, an expert witness, including a statistician, must be free to use adequate methodology for the task. In Appendix 8, we show computer code and output for the analyses in this section, using the well-regarded statistical system R, which is freely and universally available.

To illustrate appropriate methodology for analysing data on counts of deaths in different periods in the presence of other possible causal factors, consider the artificial example from Table 4 of Section 4. The deaths have been tabulated and summarised in the counts in four different categories of shifts. Note that these categories differ in various ways – they are of different durations; some are morning shifts, not all; and for some but not all the nurse in question is on duty. The rates of death vary between the extremes of 4 in 28 shifts and 2 in 2 shifts, a considerable difference, but can we attribute these differences in rate to the morning/other shift factor, or to the presence of the nurse, whilst allowing for the fact that among these small counts there will also be random variation?

⁸² See also Appendix 2.

To correctly assess the extent to which the deaths can be attributed to the presence of the nurse we must compare two hypotheses:

- (1) that the *only* cause of systematic difference in rates is the shift effect, and
- (2) that *both* the shift effect and the presence of the nurse have a systematic effect on the rates.

This way of posing the question accords with both sound scientific practice, and the criminal law principle of *in dubio pro reo*⁸³. It is incorrect, and prejudicial, simply to examine whether the presence of the nurse affects the rates whilst ignoring the other potential causal factor.

This point is illustrated in the analyses of the Table 4 “unbiased investigation” data summarised in the final rows of that Table and in Table 6. If we ignore the shift effect, we are simply comparing the rates of 10 per 15 shifts with 6 per 30 shifts when the nurse is or is not on duty. The Poisson log-linear analysis (details explained in Appendix 6, with code in Appendix 8) gives a *p*-value of 1.7% (0.017) for the likelihood ratio test that the nurse’s presence has no effect on the rates – and we would conventionally call this result significant, which would be incriminating. However, if we follow the correct practice of comparing hypotheses (1) and (2) above, the *p*-value becomes 37.8% (0.378). Because this higher *p*-value is not statistically significant, it provides no basis for rejecting hypothesis (1) and therefore cannot be incriminating. Table 6 also gives the expected numbers of deaths in each category of shifts, the maximum likelihood estimates according to the statistical models being fitted in the two approaches. It is easily verified by inspection that the values in the case of the correct analysis shown in the 6th column fit the observed data (4th column) much better than do the expected numbers under the incorrect analysis (5th column).

Table 6 Continuing the example in Table 4

Number of shifts	Nurse	Shift	Deaths	Expected deaths ignoring morning effect	Expected deaths allowing morning effect
8	on duty	morning	7	5.33	7.87
7	on duty	other	3	4.67	2.13
2	off duty	morning	2	0.40	1.13
28	off duty	other	4	5.60	4.87

⁸³ The principle that a defendant may not be convicted by a court when doubts about his or her guilt remain.

Appendix 7: Usual practice in medical statistics and epidemiology.

Two types of clusters of events are routinely investigated in medical statistics and epidemiology: outbreaks of food poisoning and clusters of severe adverse events or usually rare diseases. The difficulty of identifying possible causal factors is multi-faceted. The methods developed in medicine to bring together evidence from laboratory science, observational and experimental studies are important tools for investigation.⁸⁴

The standard first approach is to design and conduct a case-control study, a rapid and relatively inexpensive method. For each precisely defined incident, one or more control incidents are found, and the antecedents investigated. The design stage establishes clear definitions of events, and consistent approaches to seeking evidence for cases and controls. The varieties of biases which can arise are well-studied, and methods to minimise the risks of such biases established. It is standard for those recording data on possible explanatory variables to 'be blind' to which people are cases or controls. For deaths, experts in the quality and coding of death certificates might provide a necessary complement to physicians or pathologists.

In the study of causes of disease, nine aspects of association, the Bradford Hill guidelines, are considered.⁸⁵ It would be sensible to consider these in other investigations of causes, as is happening in areas of civil litigation.⁸⁶ Detailed consideration of uncertainty is preferable to false confidence in a single explanation.

Comparisons of different authorities' methods of investigating clusters of events might well lead to mutual benefit.⁸⁷ The methods in Public Health England guidelines for investigating non-infectious disease clusters possibly due to environmental exposures are relevant to clusters of death.⁸⁸ As well as suggested membership, with roles and responsibilities, of an investigation team, the guidelines include a substantial list of useful data sources.

An example of an efficient investigation is that of a cluster of serious events in children with cystic fibrosis.

- a) In 1993, doctors at Alder Hey Children's Hospital (AHCH), Liverpool, noticed that five children with cystic fibrosis (a condition in which the lungs and digestive system are clogged with thick sticky mucus) who needed surgery because of fibrosing colonopathy (obstruction of the intestine) presented between July and September, 1993. One response to this might have been to suggest that doctors at AHCH were failing in some way.
- b) On 8 January 1994, a short report was published, which reported that "The only consistent change in management had occurred 12-15 months previously when all five had switched to" high-strength pancreatic enzymes (high dose drugs).⁸⁹

⁸⁴ ICCA & RSS, 2019, Statistics and probability for advocates, p.18.

⁸⁵ Hill, AB, 1965.

⁸⁶ ICCA & RSS guide, 2019, p.19.

⁸⁷ Stewart, Ghebrehewet & Jarvis (2016).

⁸⁸ Public Health England (2019).

⁸⁹ Smyth, et al, 1994.

- c) At the time the report was published, a case-control study to investigate the findings had been started: this is the appropriate method of reacting to the reports of new adverse events among patients. The Medicines Control Agency had been informed of the cases, and had issued appropriate warnings. There were about 7600 people known to have cystic fibrosis in the UK; 5/7600 is 0.07%.
- d) On 11 November 1995, about 2 years later, the results of the case-control study were published.⁹⁰
- e) The study had 14 cases of fibrosing colonopathy, with each case matched to four controls. Data on these 70 patients showed a significant (at 5%) odds ratio of 1.45 per extra 1,000 high-strength capsules, and indicated which two particular proprietary formulations were associated with the highest odds ratios. That is, this association between particular formulations and fibrosing colonopathy could have arisen by chance one time in twenty.
- f) Laxative use was also found to be associated with fibrosing colonopathy; odds ratio 2.42 (95% Conf. Int 1.20-4.94). From a case-control study, one cannot establish whether laxative use was a cause of fibrosing colonopathy, or a symptom of it.
- g) Six of the 14 cases received care at AHCH. Care at Liverpool was associated with approximately a two-fold increase in risk of fibrosing colonopathy. If taken alone, this risk is statistically significant at the 4 percent level ($p=0.04\%$), but adjusting for high-dose drugs removes the significance ($p=0.3$ or $p=0.8$).
- h) In deciding whether to suggest that AHCH doctors were negligent, or actively harming children with cystic fibrosis, one must consider the competing explanations for fibrosing colonopathy.

⁹⁰ Smyth, et al, 1995.

Appendix 8: Annotated code and output

This appendix may be of limited interest to readers who are not statisticians, but is included for two main reasons. One, in the interests of full disclosure, is to verify the results in the illustrative numerical examples in Sections 4(f) and 5(c), and the calculations in Appendix 2, and make them completely reproducible. The other is that the codes may serve as templates for investigators and expert witnesses undertaking similar analyses in future, and a starting point for the more elaborate analyses that will be necessary in many real cases. These might entail additional explanatory factors, interactions between them, and possibly additional variables modelled as random effects. The last-mentioned here will necessitate use of generalised linear mixed models, available in R by using the lme4 package, for example.

Analysis in Table 3

Input

Create a 2 by 2 matrix containing the data for the biased investigation: deaths and survivals for the before and after cases, and display the data.

```
biased<-matrix(c(5,95,30,170),2,2)
biased
```

Conduct Fisher's test for equality of the odds ratios before and after, against the alternative that the odds on survival is less.

```
fisher.test(biased,alternative='less')
```

Repeat for the unbiased investigation

```
unbiased<-matrix(c(10,20,90,180),2,2)
unbiased
fisher.test(unbiased,alternative='less')
```

Output

Biased case

```
> biased
      [,1] [,2]
[1,]    5   30
[2,]   95  170

> fisher.test(biased,alternative='less')
```

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

```
data:  biased
p-value = 0.006818
alternative hypothesis: true odds ratio is less than 1
95 percent confidence interval:
 0.0000000 0.7151649
sample estimates:
odds ratio
```


0.2992371

Unbiased case

```
> unbiased<-matrix(c(10,20,90,180),2,2)
> unbiased
      [,1] [,2]
[1,]   10   90
[2,]   20  180
> fisher.test(unbiased,alternative='less')
```

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

```
data: unbiased
p-value = 0.5876
alternative hypothesis: true odds ratio is less than 1
95 percent confidence interval:
 0.00000 2.08157
sample estimates:
odds ratio
      1
```

Analysis in Tables 4 and 6

Input

Create data frame containing the response variables `deaths`, two explanatory factors `nurse` and `morning`, and the variable `shifts`, the number of shifts for that row of the table, used on a log-scale as an offset since we are modelling rates of deaths per unit time.

```
shifts<-c(8,7,2,28)
nurse<-as.factor(c('yes','yes','no','no'))
morning<-as.factor(c('yes','no','yes','no'))
deaths<-c(7,3,2,4)
data<-data.frame(shifts,morning,nurse,deaths)
print(data)
```

Fit Poisson log-linear models for rates of death, both with just `nurse` included as an explanatory variable, and with `morning` also included. Print analysis of deviance table and fitted values in each case

```
fitN<-glm(deaths~nurse+offset(log(shifts)),
         family=poisson(),data)
print(anova(fitN,test='Chisq'))
print(fitted(fitN))
fitMN<-glm(deaths~morning+nurse+offset(log(shifts)),
         family=poisson(),data)
print(anova(fitMN,test='Chisq'))
print(fitted(fitMN))
```

Output

Display of data frame.

	shifts	morning	nurse	deaths
1	8	yes	yes	7
2	7	no	yes	3
3	2	yes	no	2
4	28	no	no	4

Analysis of deviance table where only nurse is fitted. Note that the p -value for the nurse effect is 0.01728, ie 1.7%, so apparently statistically significant.

Analysis of Deviance Table

Model: poisson, link: log

Response: deaths

Terms added sequentially (first to last)

	Df	Deviance	Resid. Df	Resid. Dev	Pr(>Chi)
NULL			3	10.570	
nurse	1	5.6678	2	4.902	0.01728 *

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Fitted values for this model.

	1	2	3	4
	5.333333	4.666667	0.400000	5.600000

Analysis of deviance table where morning and nurse are both fitted. Note that the p -value for the nurse effect is now 0.37849, i.e. 37.8%, so is not statistically significant.

Analysis of Deviance Table

Model: poisson, link: log

Response: deaths

Terms added sequentially (first to last)

	Df	Deviance	Resid. Df	Resid. Dev	Pr(>Chi)
NULL			3	10.5699	
morning	1	8.6617	2	1.9081	0.00325 **
nurse	1	0.7756	1	1.1325	0.37849

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Fitted values for this model.

	1	2	3	4
	7.872829	2.127171	1.127171	4.872829

Biased investigation

This proceeds in exactly the same way, but using the biased data

```
deaths<-c(8,4,1,3)
```

in the input.

Analysis in Table 5

Input

Create data frame consisting of a numerical response variable `count` and two factors `nurse`, the explanatory variable, and `died`, the response category.

```
nurse<-as.factor(c('A','B','A','B'))
died<-as.factor(c('yes','yes','no','no'))
count<-c(15,9,25,31)
data<-data.frame(died,nurse,count)
print(data)
```

Fit a Poisson log-linear model, allowing for main effects `nurse` and `died`, and an interaction between them.

```
fit<-glm(count~died*nurse,data,family=poisson())
```

Output analysis of deviance table: the interaction term quantifies the differential effect of the two nurses on survival.

```
print(anova(fit,test='Chisq'))
```

The analysis of deviance table by convention uses the deviance as the test statistic: the following calculation demonstrates that it is numerically very similar to Pearson's chi-squared statistic, as defined in the text.

```
E<-c(12,12,28,28)
print(sum((count-E)^2/E))
print(2*sum(count*log(count/E)))
```

Output

Display of data frame.

	died	nurse	count
1	yes	A	15
2	yes	B	9
3	no	A	25
4	no	B	31

Analysis of deviance table. Note that the p -value for the `died:nurse` interaction is 0.1416, ie 14.2%, so not statistically significant.

Analysis of Deviance Table

Model: poisson, link: log

Response: count

Terms added sequentially (first to last)

	Df	Deviance	Resid. Df	Resid. Dev	Pr(>Chi)
NULL			3	15.3254	
died	1	13.1653	2	2.1601	0.0002852 ***
nurse	1	0.0000	1	2.1601	1.0000000
died:nurse	1	2.1601	0	0.0000	0.1416334

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Values of the two test statistics, the Pearson chi-squared statistic and the deviance statistic as used in the table above. They are very similar numerically, so it is immaterial which is used in calculating the p -value.

```
[1] 2.142857
[1] 2.160122
```

Calculations in Appendix 2

Input

Set up 4 illustrative data sets

```
casea<-matrix(c(10,30,5,35),2,2)
caseb<-matrix(c(100,300,50,350),2,2)
casec<-matrix(c(10,390,5,395),2,2)
cased<-matrix(c(55,345,5,395),2,2)
```

Define function to conduct chi-squared test, and calculate relative risk and absolute risk difference

```
comparerisks<-function(y)
{
ct<-chisq.test(y,,FALSE)
cat('statistic',ct$statistic,' p-value',ct$p.value,'\n')

risks<-y[1,]/apply(y,2,sum); cat('risks',risks,'\n')
rr<-risks[1]/risks[2]
ard<-risks[1]-risks[2]
cat('RR',rr,' AR difference',ard,'\n')
}
```

Apply function to data sets

```
casea
comparerisks(casea)
caseb
comparerisks(caseb)
casec
```

```
comparerisks(casec)
cased
comparerisks(cased)
```

Output

```
> casea
  [,1] [,2]
[1,]  10   5
[2,]  30  35
> comparerisks(casea)
statistic 2.051282 p-value 0.1520781
risks 0.25 0.125
RR 2 AR difference 0.125
> caseb
  [,1] [,2]
[1,] 100  50
[2,] 300 350
> comparerisks(caseb)
statistic 20.51282 p-value 5.923318e-06
risks 0.25 0.125
RR 2 AR difference 0.125
> casec
  [,1] [,2]
[1,]  10   5
[2,] 390 395
> comparerisks(casec)
statistic 1.698514 p-value 0.1924825
risks 0.025 0.0125
RR 2 AR difference 0.0125
> cased
  [,1] [,2]
[1,]  55   5
[2,] 345 395
> comparerisks(cased)
statistic 45.04505 p-value 1.925539e-11
risks 0.1375 0.0125
RR 11 AR difference 0.125
```


Appendix 9: Members of the working party drawing up this report

Professor Peter Green FRS, Emeritus Professor of Statistics, University of Bristol, and Distinguished Professor, University of Technology, Sydney.

Professor Richard Gill, Emeritus Professor of Statistics, Leiden University.

Neil Mackenzie QC, Arnot Manderson Advocates, Edinburgh.

Professor Julia Mortera, Professor of Statistics, Università Roma Tre.

Professor William Thompson, Professor Emeritus of Criminology, Law, and Society; Psychology and Social Behavior; and Law, University of California, Irvine.

In addition, we are grateful to Professor Jane Hutton, Professor of Medical Statistics, University of Warwick, for providing Appendix 7.

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From past to present...

The image of the sheaf of wheat first appeared in our original seal. Being the end product of the harvesting and bundling of wheat, it was a pictorial way of expressing the gathering and analysis of data: the foundations of statistical work. It also implied that statistical practice comprises more than the collection of data: it consists of active interpretation and application as well (threshed for others, if the rural analogy is sustained). Rigorous data gathering is still at the heart of modern statistics, but as statisticians we also interpret, explain and present the data we collect.

